

A thesis submitted for the
B.Sc. Honours Degree in Food Science and Technology

**A study about physicochemical and
antioxidant properties of different
brands of
'Nimba Arishta' in Sri Lanka**

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'Nimba Arishta' in Sri Lanka**

The work reported in this thesis was carried out by me in the Research and Development Centre of Link Natural Products (Pvt) Ltd. It has not been submitted for a degree in this University or any other institution.

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**This thesis is
affectionately dedicated to my
beloved parents and
lecturers as well as to
everyone who supported and motivated me.**

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Table of Contents

Acknowledgement	v
Table of Contents	vi
List of tables	ix
List of figures	ix
List of abbreviations	x
Abstract	xi
Chapter 01	1
Introduction	1
Overall objective:	4
Specific objectives	4
Chapter 02	5
Literature review	5
2.1 Ayurvedic medicines	5
2.2 Ayurvedic Polyherbal Fermented Preparations –	6
2.2.1 Fermentation in FTM	7
2.3 Arishtas –	9
2.3.1 The crucial role of <i>W. fruticosa</i> –	10
2.4 Nimba arishta –	12
2.4.1 Bark of <i>Azadirachta indica</i> (Neem) plant	14
2.4.2 <i>Terminalia bellerica</i> fruit	15
2.4.3 <i>Terminalia chebula</i> fruit.....	16
2.4.4 <i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> fruit.....	16
2.4.5 <i>Embelia ribes</i> –	17
2.5 Sensory analysis of arishta –	17
2.6 Physicochemical properties of arishtas	18
2.6.1 Total soluble solids (TSS).....	18
2.6.2 Refractive index.....	18

2.6.3 Total solid content (TDS)	19
2.6.4 Specific gravity	19
2.6.5 Total acidity and pH.....	19
2.6.6 Alcohol content.....	19
2.6.7 Total reducing sugar content –.....	20
2.6.8 Ash values –.....	21
2.7 Bioactive compounds in arishta –	21
2.7.1 Phenolic compounds	21
2.7.2. Flavonoids.....	22
2.7.3. Proanthocyanidin content	23
2.8 Antioxidant activity of arishta –.....	24
2.8.1 DPPH radical scavenging assay –.....	25
2.9 Standardization of arishta –	25
2.9.1 Problems caused by poor quality un-standardised herbal formulations	27
Chapter 03	29
Methodology.....	29
3.1 Research location.....	29
3.2 Study design	29
3.3 Collection of samples.....	29
3.4 Comparative study of properties	29
3.4.1 Sensory evaluation of Nimba arishta	30
3.4.2 Examination of physicochemical parameters of different brands of Nimba arishta.....	30
3.4.2.7 Determination of Acid-Insoluble Ash.....	33
3.4.2.8 Determination of Water-Soluble Ash	33
3.4.2.9 Determination of reducing sugar content.....	33
3.4.2.10 Determination of apparent sucrose content	36
Chapter 04	45
Results and Discussion	45
4.1 Statistical analysis:	45

4.2 Physicochemical properties of Nimba arishta samples –	45
4.2.1 pH	45
4.2.2 Brix value / Total Soluble Solids (TSS)	47
4.2.3 Refractive index	49
4.2.4 Specific gravity	50
4.2.5 - Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)	52
4.2.6 Total Ash content	54
4.2.7 Acid insoluble ash content –	56
4.2.8 Water soluble ash content –	57
4.2.9 Reducing sugar content –	59
4.2.10 Apparent sucrose content (g per 100g sample)-	60
4.2.11 Ethanol content	62
4.2.12 Total phenolic content – (TPC)	64
4.2.13 Total flavonoid content – (TFC)	66
4.2.14 Proanthocyanidin (CT) content –	67
4.3 Antioxidant activity of Nimba arishta –	69
4.3.1 DPPH Radical scavenging activity (IC₅₀)–	70
4.4 Sensory evaluation	72
Chapter 05	77
Conclusion	77
Recommendations	78
References	79
Appendices	87

List of tables

Table 4.1 - Results of pH for different brands of Nimba Arishta	47
Table 4.2 - Results of brix for different brands of Nimba Arishta	49
Table 4.3 - Results of refractive index for different brands of Nimba Arishta	51
Table 4.4- Results of specific gravity for different brands of Nimba Arishta	53
Table 4.5 - Results of total dissolved solids for different brands of Nimba Arishta	54
Table 4.6 - Results of total ash content for different brands of Nimba Arishta	56
Table 4.7 - Results of acid insoluble ash content for different brands of Nimba Arishta .	58
Table 4.8 - Results of water soluble ash content for different brands of Nimba Arishta ..	59
Table 4.9 - Results of Reducing sugar content for different brands of Nimba Arishta	61
Table 4.10 - Results of apparent sucrose content for different brands of Nimba Arishta .	62
Table 4.11 - Results of ethanol content for different brands of Nimba Arishta	64
Table 4.12 - Results of total polyphenolic content for different brands of Nimba Arishta	66
Table 4.13 - Results of total flavonoid content for different brands of Nimba Arishta	67
Table 4.14 - Results of Proanthocyanidin content for different brands of Nimba Arishta	69
Table 4.15 - Results of antioxidant activity for different brands of Nimba Arishta	71
Table 4.16 - Mean ranks of sensory evaluation of different brands of Nimba arishta	74

List of figures

Figure 1.1 - The general preparation process of Arishtas – Ayurveda Pharmacopoeia.....	1
Figure 1.2 - Different formula for making Nimba arishta – Ayurveda formula, Ayurveda act no:31, 1961	2
Figure 4.1 -Interval plot of pH versus different brands	488
Figure 4.2 -Interval plot of brix versus different brands	50
Figure 4.3 -Interval plot of refractive index versus different brands	52
Figure 4.4 -Interval plot of specific gravity versus different brands	53
Figure 4.5 -Interval plot of TDS versus different brands	55
Figure 4.6 -Interval plot of total ash content versus different brands	48
Figure 4.7 -Interval plot of acid insoluble ash content versus different brands	59
Figure 4.8 -Interval plot of water soluble ash content versus different brands	60
Figure 4.9 -Interval plot of reducing sugar content versus different brands	62
Figure 4.10 -Interval plot of apparent sucrose content versus different brands	63
Figure 4.11 -Interval plot of ethanol content versus different brands	65
Figure 4.12 -Interval plot of TPC versus different brands	67
Figure 4.13 -Interval plot of TFC versus different brands	68
Figure 4.14 -Interval plot of CT versus different brands	480

List of abbreviations

AU	Absorbance Units
CT	Condensed Tannins
TSS	Total Soluble Solids
TDS	Total Dissolved Solids
TPC	Total Phenolic Content
TFC	Total Flavonoid Content
DPPH	2,2 – diphenyl -1- picrylhydrazyl
FTM	Fermented Traditional Medicines
ORAC	Oxygen Radical Absorbance Capacity
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
GC-FID	Gas Chromatography - Flame Ionization Detection
WHO	World Health Organization
ABTS	2,2-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid)
NH ₄ Fe(SO ₄) ₂	ammonium ferric sulphate
TLC	Thin Layer Chromatography

Abstract

Ayurvedic arishtas are self-fermented polyherbal formulations and Nimba arishta is a widely used ayurvedic drug. The present study was aimed to evaluate variations in different formulations of Nimba arishta using six different commercially available brands of Nimba arishta (A,B,C,D,E and F). They were thoroughly evaluated for their organoleptic characteristics, physicochemical parameters, and antioxidant activity. A sensory evaluation on taste and odour attributes was performed. The physicochemical parameters evaluated were pH, specific gravity, brix, refractive index, total ash, acid insoluble ash, water-soluble ash, reducing sugar content, sucrose content, alcohol content, total dissolved solid content, total phenolic, flavonoid and proanthocyanidin contents. In vitro antioxidant activity was performed by DPPH assay. The results of the study were found within these ranges ; pH 3.01(D) - 3.64(A), refractive index 1.3725 (A) - 1.4019(C), specific gravity 1.0684(A)-1.0864(F), brix 25.06(A) - 41.00(C), ethanol content (V/V %) 7.65(C) – 10.4(A), total dissolved solids (g/mL) 0.1993(A) - 0.4107(C), reducing sugar content (g /100g sample) 15.75(A) - 34.24(C), apparent sucrose content (g/100g sample) 0.69(B) - 7.69(E), total ash content (w/w%) 0.0971(D) – 0.1070(A), water soluble ash content (w/w%)(0.004(B) - 0.0899(F), acid insoluble ash content (w/w%) 0.0131(D) - F-0.0571(F), total phenolic content (tannic acid equivalents in mg/ g sample) 1.7275(A) - 9.727(F), total flavonoid content (quercetin equivalents in mg/g of sample) 1.2410(A) - 3.2151(B), proanthocyanidin content (AU) 0.01027(F) - 0.1349(A), DPPH radical scavenging activity (IC₅₀) (µg/ml) 35.76(F) - 48.04(A). These results highlighted formulation variations among the different brands of Nimba arishta, emphasizing the need for standardized arishtas.

Key words: Nimba arishta, standardization, ayurvedic, physicochemical, antioxidant

Chapter 01

Introduction

Ayurveda is a traditional Indian medicinal system that has been practiced for thousands of years. Ayurveda has a rich and ancient tradition of utilizing polyherbal drugs and formulations to address a wide range of health conditions. (Nandre et al., 2012) Ayurvedic practitioners have been utilizing fermentation techniques for centuries to enhance the effectiveness of medicines and to extract and conserve the active components present in medicinal plants. Ayurveda comprises of various types of medicines including the fermented forms namely arishtas (fermented decoctions) and asavas. These are regarded as valuable therapeutics due to their efficacy and desirable features. (Nandre et al., 2012)

Arishtas are self-fermented ayurvedic medicines prepared by blending a decoction of various parts of different plants with sugar and bee honey. In Ayurveda pharmacopoeia in Sri Lanka (1976), 32 arishtas are described.

Figure 1.1 - The general preparation process of Arishtas – Ayurveda Pharmacopoeia

In most arishtas, dried flowers of *Woodfordia fruticosa* L. Kurz (Lythraceae) ('malitha mal' in Sinhala) are added as the fermentation initiator, supplemented with dried parts of other plants, together known as the 'Kalka'. But there are some arishtas, to which *W. fruticosa* is not intentionally added. Nimba arishta is one type of such arishtas where dried flowers of *W. fruticosa* are not added.

There are differences in the preparation method and the ingredients of same arishtas, resulting in the variations in the quality parameters of the final product. According to ayurvedic pharmacopoeia, there are 2 formulae for making *Nimba arishta*.

Figure 1.2 - Different formulas for making Nimba arishta – Ayurveda formula, Ayurveda act no:31, 1961

<p><u>Formula 1 –</u> <u>ingredients of making the decoction for Nimba arishta - bark of Azadirachta indica</u> water <u>as ‘Kalka’</u> <u>material, sugar</u> bee honey <i>Embelia ribes</i> (walangasal) Are added.</p>	<p><u>Formula 2-</u> <u>ingredients of making the decoction for Nimba arishta - bark of Azadirachta indica - neem</u> <i>Terminalia bellerica</i> <i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> <i>Terminalia chebula</i> <u>As ‘kalka,’</u> <i>Terminalia bellerica</i> <i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> <i>Terminalia chebula</i> Are added.</p>
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In the case of formula 2, the composition of the kalka also includes those plants which are used for decoction preparation.

Arishtas are used for treatment of a great variety of diseases, and as a tonic. According to ayurveda physicians, the fermented preparations have a moderate strength and are therefore prescribed during the recovery stage of an illness. Nimba Arishta is utilized in Sri Lanka to treat rashes and gout, purify the blood, and act as an anthelmintic.

Therapeutic application of these arishtas is based on the properties of the ingredients and the method of preparation. Because of the changes in the production process used by different manufacturers, there can be variations in the quality parameters of organoleptic, physicochemical characteristics and antioxidant activity of arishtas. Since plant materials are used, the content of the extracted ingredients may be varied depending on the identity, purity, quality and maturity level of the plant materials, their source of origin and on the fermentation process. There is

uncertainty about the exact ingredients from which the fermentation process is initiated in Nimba arishta, unless a specific fermentation initiator is intentionally added. Even though, *W. fruticosa* is added in other arishta types as an important ingredient essential for the regulation of the fermentation process, their impact is also not clearly identified yet.

If commercially available Nimba Arishtas differ considerably with regard to their physical and chemical composition, there's a problem with these products about their quality, safety and efficacy in providing expected outcomes.

In Sri Lanka, all arishtas from commercial sources, are marketed under the traditional names mentioned in the Ayurveda Pharmacopoeia. The presence of identical names for preparations from different manufacturing companies might lead to the assumption of uniformity among the products. However, considering the differences in the recipes of Nimba arishta, it is expected that the physicochemical parameters of these products will exhibit variations. The absence of specific recipe or ingredient information on the label of Nimba arishta, creates a perception of uniformity among these products within the market.

To investigate those variations, same type of arishta, 'Nimba arishta' produced from different manufacturers in Sri Lanka are analysed and compared by this study.

The popularity as well as market of Ayurvedic medicines has been increasing day by day in the country. As there is no well-established mechanism for standardization and monitoring so far within the country to assure and control the quality of such medicines, many questions are raised regarding the quality, safety and efficacy of these medicines.

This research would lead to the emergence of the need to have a national standardization in Ayurveda arishtas.

1.1 Objectives

Overall objective:

To study and analyse the physicochemical and antioxidant properties of ‘Nimba arishta’ commercially produced by different manufacturers in Sri Lanka.

Specific objectives:

1. To study the previously reported physicochemical and biological activities of Nimba arishta.
2. To evaluate the organoleptic parameters of Nimba arishta
3. To analyse physicochemical properties of six reputed commercial samples of Nimba arishta
4. To evaluate the in vitro antioxidant properties of six commercial samples of Nimba arishta.
5. To compare sensory, physicochemical and in vitro antioxidant properties among different brands of Nimba arishta

Chapter 02

Literature review

2.1 Ayurvedic medicines -

Ayurveda is considered by many scientists to be the oldest healing science. The word is a combination of “Ayur”, meaning ‘life’ and “Veda” meaning ‘science’. Literally translated from Sanskrit, Ayurveda means “the science of prolonging life”. (Nandre et al., 2012). Ayurvedic pharmacology is a vast and intricate discipline that focuses on the preparation of herbal and mineral compounds. Although the majority of studies investigating Ayurvedic interventions have been conducted in India, there is growing interest in Ayurveda in other parts of the world.

Ayurvedic herbal medicines encompass a range of products, including herbs, herbal materials, herbal preparations, and finished herbal products, that utilize parts of plants, either alone or in combination as the primary source of active ingredients. (General guidelines for methodologies on research and evaluation of traditional medicine, World Health Organization, Geneva, 2000). According to the WHO, traditional medicinal plants are the primary source of healthcare for around 80% of the population in developing countries. (Kumar et al., 2016). Ayurvedic herbal dosage forms are formulated by the incorporation of active ingredients through different manufacturing processes.

Since synthetic products are known to have adverse effects, there has been a growing interest in using herbal systems for disease management. There are significant evidence supporting the effectiveness of herbs in the treatment of various human diseases, disorders, and illnesses. (Luqman et al., 2014).

Ayurvedic remedies are often considered as a cost-effective, inherently safe and with lesser incidence of side effect. Ayurveda aims to promote good health and prevent disease through a holistic approach that includes lifestyle modifications, dietary recommendations, herbal remedies, and other natural therapies. (Bouldin et al., 1999). To improve the therapeutic efficacy of Ayurvedic herbs, it is important to ensure that they meet modern standards for identity, purity, safety, drug content, and physical and biological properties. This can be achieved by employing scientific approaches to assess and enhance the quality of the herbs. (Patwardhan, 2005; Kulkarni et al., 2012a).

The integration of modern scientific tools and techniques in the evaluation of Ayurvedic medicines highlights their continued significance even today, presenting a promising opportunity for their application in global disease management. (Tiwari, 2005).

2.2 Ayurvedic Polyherbal Fermented Preparations –

Fermentation can be prescribed as a technique for drug preparation in Ayurveda. Fermentative technology is a unique feature exclusive to Ayurveda, setting it apart from other systems of medicine. The practice of ayurveda has long utilized fermentation processes to enhance the potency of medicinal drugs and extract and preserve active components from medicinal herbs. (Sabu & Haridas, 2015a).

Ayurveda holds unique position among traditional medicinal practices for its utilization of polyherbal Fermented Traditional Medicines (FTM) namely arishta (fermented decoctions) and asava (fermented infusions). Asavas are alcoholic medicaments prepared from powdered herbal drugs and arishtas are alcoholic medicaments prepared from decoctions of herbal drugs. The end result consistently yielded a medicated wine. These potent polyherbal formulations are utilized as appetizers and stimulants, known for their high efficacy. (H. Singh et al., 2010)

Typically, the physician determines the use of asavas or arishtas based on the patient's specific condition. Asava and arishta are highly valued in Ayurveda due to their unique characteristics that make them superior to other forms of medicine. They are effective, palatable, stable and most notably they lack adverse effects. These fermented formulations are generally regarded as superior to tinctures in terms of gut absorption since they are partially digested. (Sabu & Haridas, 2015a). The fermentation process breaks down complex compounds in the herbs, making the nutrients more easily absorbed by the body. This enhances the overall efficacy of the herbal blend and allows for better assimilation of its medicinal properties.

Arishta and Asava were used to treat various diseases in pediatrics, nervous system, blood and circulatory system, respiratory system, digestive and excretory systems, urinary system, reproductive system, immune system, general ailments, skin problems, infectious diseases and other problems like poisonous bites.

The presence of alcohol in the preparation of asava and arishta offers numerous benefits such as improved shelf-life, enhanced therapeutic efficacy, increased extraction efficiency of active

compounds from medicinal plants, and better absorption of drugs in the human body. (Sekar & Vinothkanna, 2019).

Moreover, these fermented preparations are often regarded as natural probiotics. The fermentation process encourages the growth of beneficial bacteria, which can help improve gut health and enhance the body's immune response. While the medicinal properties of Ayurvedic FTM are attributed to the phytochemicals present in the herbs, it is possible that the antioxidant activity of bacterial isolates may also contribute to their overall medicinal benefits. (Vinothkanna & Sekar, 2019).

2.2.1 Fermentation in FTM

The process of fermentation involves the breakdown or conversion of substrates into compatible components through microbial enzymes, resulting in the improvement of substrate properties and the enrichment of bioactive compounds. (Parvez et al., 2006)

Fermentation enhances the efficacy of herbal medicines while minimizing their adverse effects. Through the process of fermentation, the plant material undergoes a reduction in the amounts of undesirable sugars, thereby increasing its bioavailability and minimizing adverse effects such as bloating and gas. (Chaudhary et al., 2011)

Through fermentation, various phytochemical compounds present in medicinal plants undergo transformations making them less toxic and more potent, thereby aiding in their absorption. (Mishra et al., 2010). During fermentation, yeast cell walls have the ability to bind heavy metals and pesticide residues, thereby acting as a natural cleansing system. This process not only removes contaminants from the plant material but also reduces the toxicity of certain harmful components present in the herbs. This makes fermentation of herbal products potentially safer than other methods such as powder or tinctures. (Chaudhary et al., 2011)

The process of fermentation breaks down the cells of the herb, allowing them to be more easily exposed to the menstruum. It also facilitates the transportation of dissolved constituents from the herbal material into the menstruum, creating an active transport system. Additionally, bacteria present during fermentation produce enzymes that further assist in the leaching process by breaking down the cell walls of the herb. During fermentation, the gradual increase in alcohol

levels in the menstruum creates a gradient that allows for the extraction of a wider range of active ingredients from the herb compared to other extraction methods. (Mulay & Khale, 2011).

Fermentation has been found to increase the levels of bioactive compounds like antioxidants, reducing the potential risk of ethanol-induced hepatotoxicity and enhance the anti-inflammatory properties of various compounds. (Ng et al., 2011). T. Kumar et al., 2013 reported that self-fermented products have the potential to undergo ongoing chemical transformations that extend beyond the hydro-alcoholic extraction of suspended material. This may lead to the creation of novel natural molecules with enhanced therapeutic properties. These phytochemicals have demonstrated beneficial effects on long-term health when consumed by humans and can effectively treat various human diseases. So that the fermentation process plays a significant role in enhancing the pharmacological properties of herbal medicines by transforming naturally occurring compounds, including isoflavones, saponins, phytosterols, and phenols, which possess beneficial health-promoting and disease-preventing effects, in accordance with the principles of Oriental medicine. (Lee et al., 2003).

Though arishta and asava are preparations from plant materials, the role of micro-organisms in this fermentation process is not at all realized. The inherent microbes in the fermentation process may serve multiple functions. Microbial enzymes can exhibit distinct reactions in aqueous and organic phases, with the ability to catalyze reactions that may not be possible in a purely aqueous environment. (Stepankova et al., 2013).

Microbes may have a multifaceted role in the fermentation process, including the production of antimicrobial compounds, antioxidants, immunomodulators, and other pharmaceuticals. These could be in addition to the phytochemicals already present in the herbal materials. Microbes may also have the ability to bioconvert phytochemicals into nanomedicines, and even create nanoparticles if metal components are used in the preparation. The ability of microbes to detoxify (Phengnuam & Suntornsuk, 2013) to convert metal nanoparticles (T. Singh et al., 2017) and to form nanomedicines (Watkins et al., 2015) are well established.

Since microbes are ingested along with these medicines, they can act as probiotics and provide various health benefits. For instance, probiotics can help in digestion by stimulating proteolytic, lipolytic, amylolytic, and cellulolytic activity. They can also remove phytic acid from grain-based food by having phytase activity, digest lactose by possessing β -galactosidase activity, modulate the immune and nervous system, reduce serum cholesterol levels, and maintain blood lipid profiles, among other things. (Hemarajata & Versalovic, 2013).

Probiotics have many more numerous benefits for patients, such as the treatment of acute diarrhea, prevention of antibiotic-associated diarrhea, alteration of intestinal microbiota, avoidance of *Helicobacter pylori* colonization in the stomach, prevention of cancer and colon tumors, combating allergies, regulating blood pressure, and preventing dental and vaginal infections. (Kechagia et al., 2013). There are many other promising effects of probiotics that are not limited to the ones mentioned so far. (George Kerry et al., 2018)

The addition of sweeteners such as sugar, honey, or jaggery to specific ingredients, as well as the proportion and the stage of their addition, can significantly impact the alcoholic extraction of therapeutic properties during fermentation. (Deshpande et al., 2016)

The studies mentioned above support the speculated benefits of polyherbal FTM, as described in Ayurvedic classics.

2.3 Arishtas –

Submerged fermentation mediated by intrinsic microorganisms is the distinctive process utilized to produce Arishta, a polyherbal product. Arishtas are typically comprised of primary herbs, which are often used as the basis for naming the product, as well as herbal flavoring agents, herbal fermentation initiator or kalka, and a source of sugar derived from plants.

The initial step in the preparation of arishta involves the preparation of a decoction of the herbal ingredients, according to the recipe. Decoction is prepared by boiling herbs in the recommended quantity of water until the volume is reduced to one-fourth. It is a method of extracting active compounds from medicinal plant materials. The decoction extracts a higher concentration of flavonoids and phenolics from medicinal plant materials than an infusion. The process involves simmering the herbs in water over low to moderate heat for a prolonged period. This continuous mild heating helps in extracting the water-soluble components of the herbal drug. However, if the mixture is heated excessively or at too high a temperature, it may result in the charring of the plant material, leading to the loss of therapeutic properties. (Sayyad et al., 2012).

The addition of sugar, such as jaggery or honey, or a combination of both, serves as a substrate for fermentation in the preparation of arishta. Later in the preparation, kalka, are added to improve the color and aroma of the final product and aid in the assimilation of the medicinal properties. (Kulkarni et al., 2012b).

This initial stage of anaerobic fermentation involves the gradual accumulation of ethanol and release of CO₂. The resulting aqueous-alcoholic milieu may extract a wide range of phytochemicals. The fermentation vessel is then left undisturbed for at least a month (and up to six months in some cases). During this period, further microbial action may promote the biotransformation of phytochemicals, and there may not be any evolution of gases.

Microbes that are either naturally present in the ingredients or acquired during the process are responsible for carrying out the fermentation. (Sekar & Vinothkanna, 2019).

Prior to fermentation, the liquid has a dark brown color, is thick in consistency and maintained room temperature. Once fermentation began, the color of the mixture slightly lightened, and a mild alcoholic odor could be detected. The presence of effervescence could be observed, and a distinct sound is heard from the vicinity of the container. When a burning matchstick is brought near the surface of the fermenting liquid, it is extinguished due to the production of CO₂. After fermentation is complete, the color of the decoction is lightened, and the consistency becomes thinner compared to before fermentation. (Bore & Wadnerwar, 2021).

Research has revealed that when used as a consortium, even yeast isolates that were individually less effective in producing alcohol were more efficient in producing and mobilizing targeted active phytoconstituents. (Mishra et al., 2010). Furthermore, studies have indicated that the temperature during the fermentation process of arishtas plays a significant role. In the case of hot decoction formulations, the yeast cells were destroyed due to the higher temperature, rendering the fermentation process unfavorable. On the other hand, in cold decoctions, the yeast cells had remained intact, making it favorable for the fermentation process. (Deshpande et al., 2016).

There have been research comparing traditional and modern methods of preparations of arishtas. According to (Shingadiya et al., 2016) study, arishta prepared using classical methods have shown greater efficacy compared to those prepared using modified techniques.

2.3.1 The crucial role of *W. fruticosa* –

W. fruticosa dried flowers are commonly used to initiate and regulate the fermentation process in many arishtas. During the preparation of alcoholic medicaments in Ayurvedic Systems, the wild species of yeast that can withstand high sugar concentration are obtained from the flowers of *W. fruticosa*. These flowers serve as the inoculum for the yeasts used in the process. The dried

flowers of *W. fruticosa* facilitate the growth of inherent yeasts, regulate the fermentation process, and provide a source of immunomodulators. These flowers are rich in nectar and tannins, which are primarily located in the dry nectariferous area where yeast spores are present. Das et al. demonstrated that the flowers of *W. fruticosa* contain a significantly high concentration of tannins, up to 22%. The tannins create a favorable environment for the growth of yeasts. (Mishra et al., 2010). These polyphenolic compounds are susceptible to enzymatic conversion into simple phenols and alcohol during the anaerobic fermentation of Arishta preparations. (Chaudhary et al., 2011)

In ancient times, fermentation of herbal materials was solely attributed to native microbes. The practice of using the dried flowers of *Madhuca longifolia* precedes the use of *W. fruticosa* flowers. However, it is important to note that the use of *W. fruticosa* flowers contributes significantly to the therapeutic properties of the medicament as they act as immunomodulatory agents. (B. H. Kroes, van den Berg, et al., 1993)

W. fruticosa flowers may have a critical role in regulating the initial stage of anaerobic fermentation for ethanol production. Ayurvedic practitioners and manufacturers of Ayurvedic medicines in Sri Lanka add *W. fruticosa* flowers to regulate the fermentation process and facilitate the production of alcohol. (B. H. Kroes, Van Den Berg, Abeysekerab, et al., 1993). This is a submerged fermentation process, and it is possible that a microbial consortium comprising multiple species was involved, as in other similar systems. (Wang et al., 2016) but dominated by yeasts. In the second stage, where anaerobic conditions persist in a water-ethanol environment, it is probable that dynamic changes occur in microbial diversity and population. (Sekar & Vinothkanna, 2019). The use of fresh *W. fruticosa* flowers can boost the fermentation process, resulting in a higher alcohol content compared to when dried flowers are used. (Kulkarni et al., 2012b).

It is believed that flowers of *W. fruticosa* are the source of the inoculum. The impact of *W. fruticosa* flowers on the alcohol and sugar contents of Nimbāriṣṭa has been investigated. (B. H. Kroes, Van Den Berg, Labadie, et al., 1993a). It has been discovered that *W. fruticosa* flowers are not the source of alcohol-producing microorganisms, but they exhibit invertase activity that may be responsible for the effect. Even though *W. fruticosa* is commonly used as the starter in traditional ayurvedic medicines, there are several āsava or ariṣṭa recipes that do not include them. (Thomas et al., 2016).

In contrast, Das et al. have proposed different findings. They suggest that an endogenous invertase (fructofuranosidase) present in *W. fruticosa* flowers facilitates sucrose hydrolysis to produce alcohol. This alcohol production promotes the extraction of biologically active components, including gallic acid, from the plant materials and facilitates absorption of active principles in the gastrointestinal tract. Moreover, this alcohol can resist the growth of microorganisms in arishta preparations for extended periods of time. The increased content of gallic acid, which is usually present in small amounts, along with the Ayurvedic method of "self-generating alcohol," implies a possible connection. Based on their research, the earlier referred researchers tried to establish that *W. fruticosa* flowers are an essential component of arishta preparations, not only for initiating fermentation but also for enhancing clinical efficacy. (Chaudhary et al., 2011).

This idea is backed by the fact that in some formulations, *W. fruticosa* is not a mandatory ingredient, suggesting that its role is not solely as a carrier of inoculums. (Chaudhary et al., 2011).

A study conducted on the production of Kumariasava showed that the addition of *W. fruticosa* flowers to a sterilized mixture of ingredients did not result in alcoholic fermentation. However, in the regular preparation of Kumariasava, alcohol was produced regardless of the presence of *W. fruticosa* flowers, which suggests that the flowers are not the only source of organisms responsible for fermentation. (Deshpande et al., 2016).

In some formulations, the recipes do not contain sources of inoculum to initiate fermentation. It is possible that flowers of *M. longifolia*, which are present in a few formulations, may harbor microorganisms capable of fermenting sugar into alcohol. (Thomas et al., 2016)

Apart from these flowers, since the other ingredients like kalka and honey are added they also contain wild yeasts to initiate the process of fermentation. In addition to the flowers, the other ingredients such as kalka and honey also contain wild yeasts that can initiate the fermentation process.

2.4 Nimba arishta –

Nimba Arishta is a popular arishta commonly used in Sri Lanka. It is produced and sold in large quantities by various pharmaceutical companies and is widely prescribed by physicians to use in the treatment of eg. skin diseases (rashes) or as a tonic. (Horsten et al., 1990)

Nimba arishta is prepared mainly from the bark of (neem plant) *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. (Meliaceae)(Nimba in Sanskrit). Other than that, fruit pericarps of *Terminalia chebula* Retz. (Combretaceae), *Terminalia bellerica* Roxb. (Combretaceae), and *Phyllanthus emblica* L. (Euphorbiaceae) are added as the kalka material. Apart from those, in some formulations *Embelia ribes* is added as the Kalka material.

The production process of Nimba arishta involves first preparing a decoction using minced *A. indica* bark. Sometimes, fruit pericarps of *T. chebula*, *T. bellerica*, and *P. emblica* are added as minor ingredients. After filtration, a large amount of sucrose (up to 50% w/v) and a kalka made from various powdered plant materials and intact dried flowers of *W. fruticosa* are added to the decoction. The mixture is then left to ferment in an air-tight sealed vessel for one month. (B. H. Kroes, Van Den Berg, Labadie, et al., 1993b). But in according to Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia, Nimba arishta is produced in the absence of *W. fruticosa* Kurz.

The authors of a study have analyzed the impact of *W. fruticosa* flowers on the immunomodulatory activity, as well as the alcohol and sugar contents of Nimba arishta. Their findings revealed that the yeasts present in the *W. fruticosa* flowers played a significant role in the production of ethanol during the Ayurvedic fermentation process. (B. H. Kroes, Van Den Berg, Labadie, et al., 1993b)

The flowers of *W. fruticosa* play an important role in the production of Nimba arishta. They help preserve the arishta by contributing to the hydrolysis of sucrose, which increases the osmolarity of the mixture and enhances alcohol production. Additionally, the gallic acid released by the flowers acts as an antioxidant, further aiding in the preservation process. (B. H. Kroes, Van Den Berg, Abeysekera et al., 1993)

During an investigation of ayurvedic preparation methods of Nimba arishta, it was found that a white and a yellow strain of *Aspergillus niger* v. Tieghem were growing on the surface of the fermentation broth during the initial days of the fermentation process. (Horsten1990, n.d.) studied hydrolysis of gallotannins by two *A. niger* strains isolated from a model preparation of nimba arishta.

A. niger is known to contain tannases that can convert gallotannins. *W. fruticosa* flowers contain gallotannins, which can sometimes be as high as 20%. Other molds and bacteria were also found in *W. fruticosa* flower material, but they were not present in model preparations of Nimba arishta. The conditions of the fermentation broth, including high sugar content, alcohol, and low pH,

allowed the growth of only *A. niger* strains. (Horsten et al., 1990). In another study, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* were isolated from Nimbarishta. (B. H. Kroes, Van Den Berg, Labadie, et al., 1993b).

Fermentation in the presence of *W. fruticosa* flowers resulted in an increase of the gallic acid content. The conversion of gallotannins to gallic acid by *A. niger* during the fermentation process may contribute to the immunomodulating properties of Nimba arishta. (Horsten et al., 1990)

A study on the fermentation of Nimba arishta with *W. fruticosa* flowers reported that the flowers play a role in the formulation by releasing enzymes such as invertase, but not by yeasts. The addition of *W. fruticosa* flowers to Nimba arishta formulation releases enzymes like invertase which catalyze the hydrolysis of sucrose. However, the fermentation process triggered with these flowers was initially slow due to the limited availability of active yeast cells from the nectarproducing region, which are necessary for fermentation. It took about a week to build an effective population of cells to begin fermentation. The slow fermentation could also be attributed to the presence of anti-invertase compounds in the *W. fruticosa* flowers.

The influence of microorganisms introduced by adding *W. fruticosa* on the alcohol content of Nimba arishta was investigated. To do so, the flowers were added to a sterilized decoction containing sucrose, but no alcohol was detected in this model preparation. This suggests that the alcohol content of 6-10% (w/v) found in commercial Nimba arishtas is not due to microorganisms introduced through the addition of *W. fruticosa* flowers. (B. H. Kroes et al., 1990).

2.4.1 Bark of *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) plant

In ayurvedic medicine in Sri Lanka, *A. indica* A. Juss. ('Nimba' in Sanskrit) (Meliaceae) is used in the treatment of skin diseases, inflammation and fever. (B. H. Kroes, Van Den Berg, Abeysekerab, et al., 1993).

There are three major classes of plant secondary metabolites, namely alkaloids, phenols and terpenoids. (Das & Gezici, 2018). This bark contains mainly isoprenoids; diterpenoids (nimbinosol, nimbinone, nimosone, nimbonone, nimbosone, etc), triterpenoids, and other glycerides, polysaccharides, flavonoids and other glycosides.

The bark of neem contains around 14% tannins, which is comparable to the tannin content of other trees commonly used for tannin extraction. The main trunk bark includes tricyclic diterpenoids, NB-II peptidoglycan, gallic acid, gallo catechin, epigallocatechin, catechin, epicatechin, margolone, margolonone, isomargolonone and polysaccharides, all of which exhibit potent immunomodulatory, antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activities. (D. Kumar, Rahal, et al., 2016) (B. Kroes et al., 1989). Studies conducted previously have demonstrated that the decoction of bark of *A. indica* contains various compounds such as (+)-catechin, (-)-epicatechin, (+)-gallo catechin, epigallocatechin, and gallic acid. However, the neem compounds are not very soluble in water, and the alcoholic extracts are around 50 times more concentrated.

Neem is believed to have curative properties for various skin ailments and has been found to be effective in the treatment of leprosy. The decoction obtained from dried neem bark has been shown to possess anthelmintic properties and can effectively eliminate intestinal worms. In addition, nimbidiol, present in bark, can inhibit intestinal glucosidases and thus can be beneficial in controlling diabetes. The bark contains polysaccharides and limonoids that are beneficial in alleviating the risk of cancer development. (Mukherjee & Sengupta, 2013). Fermented decoction of neem bark inhibits the human complement system and polymorphonuclear cells. (B. H. Kroes, Van Den Berg, Labadie, et al., 1993b)

2.4.2 *Terminalia bellerica* fruit

T. bellerica fruit contains 20-30% tannins; gallic acid, ellagic acid, ethyl gallate, chebulagic acid and others; Bellericanins, Phyllembilin; termilignan, thaninilignan, methylene dioxy flavan and anolignan B.

The antimicrobial effect of the aqueous extract obtained from *T. bellerica* fruit has been confirmed in studies involving bacterial and fungal isolates. The presence of tannins in the fruit extract of *T. bellerica* has prevented the development of microorganisms by precipitating the microbial protein and making nutritional proteins unavailable for them.

These findings suggest that the extract contains phytochemicals capable of deactivating key cellular enzymes that are crucial for the metabolic pathways of these microorganisms. This antimicrobial activity indicates the potential of *T. bellerica* fruit extract in inhibiting the growth

and survival of bacteria and fungi, providing further insight into its mechanism of action. (Mani et al., 2014)

2.4.3 *Terminalia chebula* fruit

Phytochemical analysis of *T. chebula* shows the presence of gallic acid (1.21%), ellagic acid, tannic acid, ethyl gallate, chebulic acid, chebulinic acid, chebulagic acid, corilagin, mannitol, ascorbic acid (vitamin C), a tannin terchebin, an ellagitannin terchebulin, syringic acid, and other compounds. One source lists *T. chebula* as having 32% tannin content; hydrolyzed products are chebulic acid and a D-galloyl glucose.

In vitro studies have demonstrated the protective effects of *T. chebula* extracts on epithelial cells infected with influenza A virus. Moreover, a tannin fraction obtained from *T. chebula* has shown potential anti-mutagenic activity, and another study has observed its high potential for inhibiting the growth of leukemia cells. (Chang & Lin, 2012)

2.4.4 *Phyllanthus emblica* fruit

The active ingredient that has significant pharmacological action in *P. emblica* is designated as "Phyllemblin". The fruit is rich in quercetin, phyllaemblic compounds, gallic acid, tannins, flavonoids, pectin, terpenoids, alkaloids and vitamin C and contains various polyphenolic compounds. The phytochemicals of this plant include hydrolysable tannins (Emblicanin A, Emblicanin B, punigluconin, pedunculagin) (Ghosal et al., 1996), flavonoids (Kaempferol 3 O alpha L (6'' methyl) rhamnopyranoside, Kaempferol 3 O alpha L (6'' ethyl) amnopyranoside) (Rahman, 2007), alkaloids (Phyllantidine and phyllantine) (Khanna et al., 1975).

This wide range of phytochemical components including flavonoids, and tannins have been shown to possess useful biological effects. (E. Singh et al., n.d.)

2.4.5 *Embelia ribes* –

E. ribes berries contain several chemical constituents like volatile oil, fixed oil, resin, tannin, christembine (alkaloid), phenolic acids like caffeic acid, vanillic acid, chlorogenic acid, cinnamic acid, o-cumaric acid, quercitol, vilangin and resinoid. The main active component in *E. ribes* is Embelin, chemically 2, 5-dihydroxy-3-undecyl-1, 4- benzoquinone. (Lal & Mishra, 2013).

E. ribes is having antibacterial, antifertility, antiprotozoal, abdominal disorders, lung diseases, constipation, indigestion, fungus infections, mouth ulcer, sore throat, pneumonia, heart disease and obesity, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anthelmintic, anti-diabetic, anticonvulsant, anticancer, anti-hyper lipidemic, wound healing and molluscicidal activity.

2.5 Sensory analysis of arishta –

Sensory analysis is a quantitative field that is utilized in both the food industry and medical field. This science involves collecting numerical data to establish specific and lawful relationships between the characteristics of a product and human perception.

Sensory analysis is defined by the Institute of Food Technology as a scientific method used to elicit, measure, analyze, and interpret the responses to products perceived through the senses of sight, smell, touch, taste, and hearing. It is widely applied in various industries, including product development, product matching, product improvement, process change, cost reduction, raw material selection, quality control, product grading/rating, consumer acceptance, consumer preference, panel selection/training, and subjective/objective correlation.

Ayurvedic classics mention several quality attributes for drugs and critical endpoints for pharmaceutical operations, which are based on sensory evaluation. Therefore, it is recommended to use sensory-based analytical methods for the quality control of Ayurvedic medicines. (Mehta et al., 2020). Sensory analysis is an effective tool for obtaining valuable insights into how humans perceive changes in products caused by factors such as ingredients, processing, packaging, or shelf-life. As a measurement science, sensory analysis is concerned with precision, accuracy,

sensitivity, and minimizing the occurrence of false positive results, just like any other analytical method.

2.6 Physicochemical properties of arishtas

Fermentation of herbs has been found to cause various biochemical changes, leading to changes in the ratio of nutritive and anti-nutritive components present in the plants. These changes can have a significant impact on the properties of the final product, including its bioactivity and digestibility. (Hussain et al., 2016)

The physico-chemical properties of the fermented decoctions are analysed based on different parameters. There are few reports on the organoleptic and primary biochemical parameters of certain arishta. Physicochemical properties such as specific gravity, pH, total solid content, total soluble solids, refractive index, alcohol content, ash and reducing sugar content are important parameters, which indicate the desired quality of the arishtas.

2.6.1 Total soluble solids (TSS)

Total soluble solids are substances that can be dissolved in water and mainly includes soluble sugars and other soluble substances. TSS content of arishta is usually determined by brix value using Abbe refractometer, which is a typical instrument to detect liquid concentration using light power.

2.6.2 Refractive index

The extraction or fermentation process can result in the formation of volatile components that can alter the refractive index of the sample. (“Influence of Storage Conditions on Physico-Chemical Properties and Shelf-Life of Devdarvadyarishta,” 2021).

2.6.3 Total solid content (TDS)

Total solid content has a moderate impact over viscosity. Increase in solid content increases viscosity. Total solids are automatically inversely proportional to the percentage of alcohol. (B. H. Kroes, van den Berg, et al., 1993).

2.6.4 Specific gravity

A specific gravity is the ratio of specific weight of the material to the specific weight of the distilled water. The specific gravity was determined by dividing weight of the sample expressed in grams by the weight of the water, expressed in grams.

2.6.5 Total acidity and pH

The total acidity of arishta can vary depending on several factors, such as the ingredients used, fermentation duration, and environmental conditions. Traditional Ayurvedic texts often emphasize the sour taste as an important quality of arishta, which suggests the presence of acidic components. Organic acids such as acetic acid, ellagic acid, gallic acid are found in traces which causes an acidic pH to be found in arishta. As the storage time increases, no change in the pH value has been observed. (Chaudhary et al., 2011).

2.6.6 Alcohol content

Self-generated alcohol itself acts as a preservative and improves stability of formulation, no addition of external preservative is essential. According to Ayurvedic Pharmacopoea of India, all arishtas should have 5 to 10 % of self-generated alcohol.

It was determined by distillation method and dichromate techniques, as more reliable for alcohol content determination as distillation method shows fluctuations in repeated results due to minor

errors. In a study conducted for Saraswatarishta, alcohol was estimated by Caputi et al. (1968) method which is a spectrophotometric (dichromate) method.

Asava-arishta formulations with lower alcohol content are suitable for use in children as well as adults. However, the alcohol content should be adequate to improve digestion and absorption of food, but not high enough to cause any adverse drug reactions. Hence it should be used in prescribed limits. Methanol is absent in arishta. Hence, its presence is fatal for life. (Bore & Wadnerwar, 2021)

A simple, rapid and accurate gas liquid chromatography method has been used for separation and quantification of complex organic molecules developed during fermentation such as acetaldehyde, acetone, ethyl acetate, methanol, 2-propanol, ethanol, diacetyl, 2-butanol, 1-propanol, 2,3-pentanedione, n-butyl acetate, iso-butanol, 1-butanol, iso-amyl alcohol, 1-pentanol, acetic acid, furfural in formulation by direct injection gas chromatography.

2.6.7 Total reducing sugar content –

Sucrose is typically added at a concentration of 40-50% (w/v) for the preparation of arishtas. During the preparation, an excess amount of jaggery also may be added. Formulations with higher reducing sugar content have better nutritional value and therapeutic efficacy. They are also better absorbed by the body and produce energy more rapidly. However, over time, there can be a decrease of 60 to 80% in total reducing sugar content. Formulations with higher alcohol percentage have lower levels of reducing sugar.

In commercially available Nimba arishtas, it has been observed that glucose and fructose are present in higher amounts than other sugars. (B. H. Kroes et al., 1990)

The quantitative estimation of sugar is carried out by a titrimetric method. This method is a modification of the Lane and Eynon (1923) procedure involving the reduction of Soxhlet's modification of fehling's solution by titration at boiling point against a solution of reducing sugars in honey using methylene blue as an internal indicator.

2.6.8 Ash values –

The determination of ash value can provide information on the identity and purity of drugs and can be used as an indicator of adulteration. The acid insoluble ash content is particularly important as it can indicate contamination, substitution, adulteration, or errors in sample preparation for marketing. The presence of acid insoluble ash in a product can also indicate the absence of silicalike impurities in the drug. Water soluble ash is the difference between the weight of the total ash and the residue obtained after treatment of the total ash with water. This residue represents the extraneous matter adhering to the plant material.

2.7 Bioactive compounds in arishta –

Bioactive compounds are molecules that present therapeutic potential with influence on energy intake, while reducing pro-inflammatory state, oxidative stress and metabolic disorders. (Siriwardhana et al., 2013).

Bio active compounds are capable of modulating metabolic processes and demonstrate positive properties such as antioxidant effect, inhibition of receptor activities, inhibition or induction of enzymes, and inhibition or induction of gene expression. (Santos et al., 2019)

Fermentation in arishta leads to the decomposition and/or biotransformation of complex substrates, resulting in the formation of compatible components. This process helps modulate the properties of the final product and may also lead to changes in the quantity of certain bioactive compounds. (Parvez, Malik, Ah Kang, & Kim, 2006).

Bioactive metabolites of medicinal importance found in arishta include flavonoids, isoflavones, saponins, phytosterols, and phenolic compounds. (Hussain et al., 2016)

2.7.1 Phenolic compounds

Phenolic compounds can be grouped under phytochemicals which are plants' secondary metabolites have no major role in growth of plant. They have major roles in defence of plants, from insects and microbes. (Ali et al., 2014).

Some of the phenolic compounds found in nimba arishta include the following compounds.

Nimbin is a major polyphenolic compound present in neem. It possesses potent antiviral, antibacterial, and antifungal properties. It also exhibits anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effects.

Nimbinin is another polyphenolic compound found in neem. It has been reported to have antioxidant activity and may help in reducing oxidative stress.

Gallic acid is a phenolic acid commonly found in neem. It possesses antioxidant, antiinflammatory, and antimicrobial activities. Gallic acid has also been studied for its potential anticancer effects.

2.7.1.1 Determination of total phenolic content

The phenolic content is expressed as tannic acid equivalents, as per the Folin-ciocalteau method. (Rajalakshamy and Sindu, 2011).

Phenolics in plant extracts react with specific Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, which is a redox reagent to form a blue complex that can be quantified by visible-light spectrophotometry. (Blainski et al., 2013). The reaction forms a blue chromophore constituted by a phosphotungsticphosphomolybdenum complex, where the maximum absorption of the chromophores depends on the alkaline solution and the concentration of phenolic compounds.

The arishta with the highest phenolic content may be attributed to the conversion of water-soluble ingredients to alcohol-soluble ones, indicating fast absorption and good quality of the drug. (Singh et al., 2011; Vinothkanna et al., 2014).

2.7.2. Flavonoids –

Okwu,(2008) noted that flavonoids are water soluble super antioxidants found in plants, which prevent oxidative cell damage and have strong anti-cancer activity and inhibit all stages carcinogenesis. In addition, flavonoids are able to chelate with metals and bind with proteins. (Gang Ma et al., 2020)

Some of the flavonoids present in nimba arishta include following compounds:

Quercetin is a well-known flavonoid found in various plant sources, including neem. It exhibits antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-allergic properties. Quercetin has been studied for its potential effects on cardiovascular health, immune modulation, and anti-cancer activities.

Kaempferol is another flavonoid present in neem and other plant sources. It possesses antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. Kaempferol has also been investigated for its potential anti-cancer effects and its ability to support cardiovascular health.

Rutin is a flavonoid glycoside commonly found in neem and other plants. It exhibits antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties and is known for its potential to support blood vessel health.

Luteolin is a flavone present in neem and various other plants. It displays antioxidant, antiinflammatory, and anticancer activities. Luteolin has been investigated for its potential neuroprotective effects and its ability to modulate immune responses.

2.7.2.1 Determination of total flavonoid content

The total flavonoid content in plant extracts is determined by the aluminium chloride colorimetric assay, where Al(III) is utilized as a complexing agent. The method is based on the formation of chelates of Al(III)-flavonoids.

In this method, several factors are crucial for the formation of the flavonoid-AlCl₃ complexes and must be optimized to improve the method performance such as the reaction time, the complexant concentration, and flavonoid: herbal material ratio and the chemical structure of the polyphenol. (Silva et al., 2015).

2.7.3. Proanthocyanidin content

Tannins are tentatively classified into 2 groups: hydrolysable and condensed tannins (CT). Many tannin containing plants may include both of them.

CT are those that are not hydrolysable with such ease and are also termed proanthocyanidins. They are polymers of 2 to 50 or even more flavonoids units that are linked by C-C bonds between

flavonol sub-units. They are the most abundant secondary metabolite of land plants. (Shay et al., 2017)

Recent research also points to the role of tannins and polyphenols as the active agents in many efficacious traditional remedies; and the role of antioxidants is stressed in recent research.

2.7.3.1 Determination of Proanthocyanidin content –

The butanol-HCl-iron method is widely used for measurement of extractable proanthocyanidins (CT) in foods and feeds. As the method is based on acid catalysed oxidative depolymerization of CT into anthocyanidins, this method has been used for determination of bound CT. The modified assay is performed by mixing the sample with butanol-HCl and $\text{NH}_4\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solutions.

2.8 Antioxidant activity of arishta –

Antioxidants are secondary metabolites found naturally in most plants. An antioxidant can be defined as anything that inhibits or prevents oxidation of a substrate. (Krishnaiah et al., 2007). Free radicals are molecular species or atoms that contain one or more unpaired electrons, and they are continuously generated in the human body as a consequence of cellular metabolism. (SOUTHORN & POWIS, 1988). Free radicals play significant roles in regulating signal transduction, activating receptors, and gene expression and cause great damage to the proper functioning of the cell by readily oxidizing the proteins, unsaturated fatty acids and DNA. (Kaur and Nayyar., 2014).

In order to assess the antioxidant potential of phenolic compounds and flavonoids, various in vitro assays are used including TPC, TFC, ORAC, DPPH, and ABTS diammonium salt. The research has shown that arishta had significant activity in scavenging free radicals in in vitro assays, as well as reducing the stable radical DPPH by donating hydrogen equivalent to DPPH-H. (Wakkumbura et al., 2020). DPPH is a stable free radical because of its spare electron delocalization over the whole molecule and does not deteriorate in water, methanol, or ethanol. (Szabo et al., 2007).

Phenolic compounds, which fall under the category of polyphenols, are important secondary metabolites present in plants and are responsible for their antioxidant properties. Phenolic acids,

polyphenols, and flavonoids are types of antioxidants that have the ability to neutralize free radicals such as peroxide, hydroperoxide, or lipid peroxy, and can therefore prevent the oxidative processes that may contribute to degenerative diseases. (Kulkarni et al., 2012b). Phenolic compounds and flavonoids exhibit scavenging activity by stabilizing free radicals through their conjugated ring structures and hydroxyl groups. (Cai et al., 2006)

Antioxidants can exert their effects through various mechanisms, such as scavenging reactive oxygen or nitrogen species and inhibiting the formation of ROS. Superoxide radical, nitric oxide, and hydroxyl radical are the most common cellular free radicals.

The general consensus is that the greater the quantity of phenolic compounds in a substance, the greater its ability to scavenge free radicals in vitro. (Kulkarni et al., 2012b).

2.8.1 DPPH radical scavenging assay –

In DPPH assay, presence of hydrophilic antioxidants such as proton radical scavengers or hydrogen donors, reduces the color of DPPH to straw color from its original deep violet color at 517 nm. Moreover, the DPPH assay determines only the hydrophilic antioxidants whereas the ABTS⁺ assay measures both hydrophilic and lipophilic antioxidants. Ascorbic acid can be used as a standard for DPPH-free radical scavenging assay. (Re et al., 1999)

2.9 Standardization of arishta –

Standardizing polyherbal drugs is a complex task due to several factors that can impact the quality and purity of the raw materials, both directly and indirectly. (Randive et al., 2016)

Marketed formulations of arishta should be evaluated for physical and chemical parameters like viscosity, density, refractive index, acid value, alcohol content (Indian pharmacopoeia, 2007) to maintain the quality, safety and efficacy of product.

To date, there have been no reports on the standardization of Nimba arishta and the analysis of physicochemical parameters of this arishta.

The standardization of the formulation can be conducted in compliance with the Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India.

Physicochemical properties, such as total solid content, specific gravity, pH, density, extractive values, viscosity, reducing sugars, non-reducing sugars, alcohol, total sugar, surface tension, and refractive index, as well as phytochemical parameters, such as tannins, alkaloids, , are commonly used parameters for the standardization of asava-arishta. Some researchers have also analyzed iron, magnesium, calcium, phosphate, sulphate, ash value, sodium, and potassium contents in the asava-arishta formulations. (Deshpande et al., 2016)

Various techniques such as galvanometric, spectroscopic, and chromatographic methods, including TLC, HPTLC, and gas chromatography, have been utilized to establish standards for asava-arishta formulations.

High performance liquid chromatography is a quantitative standardization technique that can be used to compare the sample with a marker compound, fingerprinting techniques or isolate functional groups. In addition, thin layer chromatography can be used as a qualitative standardization technique to identify phytoconstituents and establish standards for comparison.

Ensuring a standardized extraction time is crucial to achieve optimal results, as inadequate time may result in incomplete extraction, while excessively long extraction times may lead to the extraction of unwanted constituents. (Nandre et al., 2012).

The stage and method of adding additives are also important factors in the preparation of arishtaasava formulations. The stage of addition should be considered relative to the environmental conditions and the properties of the ingredients. The method of addition, such as mixing ingredients in liquid, should be carefully executed to ensure optimal clinical efficacy. These factors should be considered to produce high-quality formulations.

Implementing a sterilization process can effectively control the growth of contaminating microflora during the fermentation process, leading to a reduction in the production of undesirable and potentially toxic components. (Kulkarni et al., 2012b)

The analytical value of Ayurvedic formulations can vary depending on several factors such as the season, location of collection, place of drug preparation, temperature fluctuations, and quality of ingredients used. Therefore, it is important to check various phytoconstituents and parameters such as pesticide residue, heavy metal contaminants, and microbial load to ensure the safety and batch-to-batch consistency of the formulations. (Bore & Wadnerwar, 2021).

In an attempt to standardize Ayurvedic drugs Prabhu et al. (2011a), *Viburnum coriaceum* bark arishta was used as a model prescription. The arishta was prepared using traditional methods and

W. fruticosa flowers, and the extract of this plant is known to contain phenolic compounds. A wide range of physicochemical parameters, and a primary organic analysis on the species have been conducted, revealing the presence of bioactive molecules such as tannins, saponins, phenolic compounds (flavonoids), and other phenolic glycosides as the primary phytoconstituents. The authors have suggested that such parameters could be useful for standardizing and characterizing Ayurvedic drugs.

The authors have examined a range of physicochemical parameters, including boiling and congealing temperatures, freezing point, ethanol content, loss on drying, loss on ignition, pH, refractive index, viscosity, density, total organic content, and total free sugar, to standardize the *Viburnum coriaceum* bark arishta preparation as a model of Ayurvedic prescriptions. They had found that each Ayurvedic formulation has its unique parameters, suggesting that it is challenging to generalize standardization criteria.

Weerasooriya et al. (2006) has compared the physicochemical parameters of different fermented Ayurvedic medicines and found that they were all within a narrow range. According to (Sabu & Haridas, 2015b), such parameters are only considered for generalizing fermented Ayurvedic medicinal products as fermented products for human consumption. Thus, there arises a need to develop a multi-disciplinary approach for its efficacious quality control and standardization.

To ensure the safety and efficacy of herbal medicines, it is important that the medicinal plant parts used are authentic and free from microbial contamination. For this reason, the World Health Organization has established specific guidelines for the evaluation of safety, efficacy, and quality of herbal medicines, as a requirement for global standardization.

Improved management of manufacturing, sale, and distribution of arishta is moderately desired by all stakeholders of Ayurveda, including physicians, patients, manufacturers, and regulators. These products have extensive therapeutic uses ranging from pediatrics to geriatrics. However, there are concerns regarding their use in diabetic patients due to their high sugar content, and these issues must be addressed properly. (Chaudhary et al., 2011).

2.9.1 Problems caused by poor quality un-standardised herbal formulations.

Despite the common belief among the public that herbal medicines are safe as they are natural products, extensive scientific evidence suggests that their use is not entirely without risk. If these

products are of poor quality and do not contain standardized levels of active compounds, the risk can be multiplied many times over. The lack of quality assessments for herbal medicines is a pressing issue that needs urgent attention to ensure the safety of users. Herbal medicines are not immune to quality issues such as misidentification, lack of standardization, contamination, substitution, deliberate adulterations, incorrect preparation/dosage, inappropriate or incomplete labeling/advertising. When these quality issues are present, the efficacy of the herbal medicine can be variable or non-existent, and in some cases, they can even cause toxicity.

The lack of availability of authentic raw materials is a critical issue in the preparation of Ayurvedic drugs. Due to the rarity of the original plant materials, the substitution of related species in numerous medicinal preparations without appropriate scientific evaluation is still ongoing.

Adulteration in medicinal preparations can significantly damage the reputation of the Ayurvedic system of medicine, making it a critical problem for the Ayurvedic industry to address. (Shahid et al., 2018).

To bring herbal drugs up to the standards set by the WHO and promote the practice of Ayurveda worldwide, it is necessary to evaluate the chemical constituents and pharmacological properties of plants before using them as substitutes.

Currently, there is a lack of standardized mechanisms for monitoring and controlling the quality of Ayurvedic medicines within the country. This has led to concerns regarding their quality, safety, and efficacy, which may stem from problems in their production, prescription, and marketing practices. Consequently, substandard Ayurvedic medicines could be available in the market, which not only diminishes public trust in Ayurvedic medicines but also poses a risk to public health and damages the reputation of Ayurvedic physicians and the Ayurveda system in general. (Mani Adhikari Bal Mukunda Regmi & Mani Adhikari, 2008).

Chapter 03

Methodology

3.1 Research location

This study was conducted at the Research and Development Centre, Link Natural Products (Pvt) Ltd, Malinda, Kapugoda.

3.2 Study design

This study follows an exploratory and descriptive approach, relying on data collected during a specific timeframe (January-May 2023) for the intended purpose.

3.3 Collection of samples

Nimba Arishta samples of different manufacturers were collected from the districts of Colombo and Kandy. Those samples were identified as A, B, C, D, E and F.

3.4 Comparative study of properties

Following studies on the physicochemical and organoleptic properties of the samples were performed.

3.4.1 Sensory evaluation of Nimba arishta

Samples from six different manufacturers were subjected to sensory evaluation using the internal trained sensory panel of R&D, Link Natural Products (Pvt) Ltd. The sensory panel comprised of 10 trained members.

First the samples from six different brands were evaluated organoleptically based on seven attributes; herbaceous odour, medicinal odour, aromatic odour, sour taste, sweet taste, bitter taste, astringent taste in order to assess the variations among different brands of the same arishta type. The sensory properties were presented on a five-point hedonic scale.

The data obtained from the sensory evaluation was analyzed by using Minitab 17 software (version - Minitab® 19.2020.1) with Kruskal-Wallis test method under non-parametric analysis. The average point number for each of the attributes was calculated.

3.4.2 Examination of physicochemical parameters of different brands of Nimba arishta

3.4.2.1 Determination of pH

pH was measured according to the method described in The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India -2.4.24

A digital pH meter was calibrated against standard buffer solutions. The arishta sample was mixed well to homogenize and the pH value was measured using the calibrated pH meter (bench 700 series). The determination was carried out at temperature of 23°C.

3.4.2.2 Determination of TSS

The brix value (total soluble solids) of samples were measured using digital Abbe refractometer (Biobase BK-R2S).

3.4.2.3 Determination of refractive index

The Abbe refractometer (Biobase BK-R2S) was used to measure the refractive index at 23 °C according to the method described in Indian Pharmacopoeia-2018: 2.4.27.

3.4.2.4 Determination of specific gravity

Specific gravity was measured according to the method described in Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India - 2018 : 3.8

A thoroughly cleaned and dried calibrated pycnometer was selected. The temperature of the substance to be examined was adjusted to about 20°C and the pycnometer was filled with it. The temperature of the filled pycnometer was adjusted to 25°C. Any excess of the substance was removed and weighed. The tare weight of the pycnometer was subtracted from the filled weight of the pycnometer. The specific gravity was determined by dividing weight of the liquid contained in the pycnometer by the weight of water contained, both determined at 25°C.

3.4.2.5 Determination of TDS

The method is given in the Indian Pharmacopoeia-2018 : 2.6.5

Apparatus:

- Shallow, flat-bottomed, flanged dishes, about 75 mm in diameter and about 25 mm deep, made of nickel or other suitable metal of high heat conductivity and which is not affected by boiling water.
- Electronic balance (Sartorius BSA 224S-CW)
- Water bath (model: Biobase SY – 2L8H)
- Moisture oven (model: BOV – V136F)

Method:

Empty weights of cleaned tared dishes were weighed and an accurate quantity of the sample was measured, placed in a tared dish, evaporated at as low a temperature as possible until the solvent is removed and heated on a water-bath until the residue is apparently dry. The dishes were

transferred to an oven and dried to constant weight at 105°C. Again, the weight after drying (W2) was measured and the percentage of solid content was calculated based on the following formula:

$$\text{Total dissolved solids (w/v \%)} = (W3 - W1) / V \times 100\%$$

W1- weight of empty dish, W3- weight of residue, V – volume of the sample

3.4.2.6 Determination of total ash content

Ash contents of the arishta samples were determined by wet ashing method - gravimetric principal, specified in Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India – 2.2.3.

Apparatus:

- Electronic balance (Sartorius BSA 224S-CW)
- Muffle furnace to be operated at 550°C (MF8-10T)
- Crucibles made in porcelain
- Airtight desiccators with silica gel desiccant
- Water bath (model: Biobase SY – 2L8H)
- Tongs

Method:

Arishta sample (10.000 g. n=3) was accurately weighed into previously cleaned and dried porcelain crucible and then it was heated over a water bath until the liquid portion was evaporated. The crucible was transferred to the muffle furnace set at 450 °C and incinerated until it was free of Black carbon particles and light grey ash was formed. Then the sample was removed from the furnace and allowed to cool in a desiccator. The weight of the crucible was obtained soon after reaching the room temperature. The process of ashing, cooling and weighing was repeated until no further loss in weight was indicated.

Ash content of the arishta sample was calculated using the following equation.

Calculation:

$$\text{Ash content (\%)} = (W1 - W2) / W_0 \times 100\%$$

Where,

W1- Weight of the crucible with residue after drying

W2 Weight of the empty crucible

Wo-Weight of the sample

3.4.2.7 Determination of Acid-Insoluble Ash

The method described in Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India – 2.2.4 was followed.

The ash obtained above was boiled for 5 minutes with 25.00 mL of dilute hydrochloric acid; the insoluble matter was collected on an ashless filter paper, washed with hot water and ignited to constant weight. The crucibles were cooled in a desiccator and weighed. The percentage of acidinsoluble ash was calculated.

3.4.2.8 Determination of Water-Soluble Ash

The method described in Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India – 2.2.5 was followed.

The ash obtained in 3.4.2.6 was boiled for 5 minutes with 25.00 mL of water and the insoluble matter was collected on an ashless filter paper, washed with hot water, and ignited for 15 minutes at a temperature not exceeding 450 °C. The weight of the insoluble matter was subtracted from the weight of the ash; the difference in weight represents the water-soluble ash. The percentage of water-soluble ash was calculated.

3.4.2.9 Determination of reducing sugar content

The amount of reducing sugar present in arishta was determined by Lane and Eynon method as described by SLS 464:1979, with some modifications.

3.4.2.9.1 Standardization of modified Fehling's solution

Apparatus and equipment:

- Electronic balance
- Titration flasks
- Volumetric flasks
- Burette
- Pipettes
- Hot plate

Reagents:**Standard invert sugar solution (10g/L aq)**

Pure sucrose (9.500g) was accurately weighed to the nearest milligram. Then 5.00mL of hydrochloric acid (approximately 36.5 percent m/m pure HCl) was added and diluted with water to about 100mL. This acidified solution was stored for several days at room temperature, and then diluted to one litre. A suitable volume of this solution was neutralized with 1N NaOH solution immediately before use and diluted to the required concentration (2g/L) for the standardization.

Methylene blue indicator:

Methylene blue indicator (2.000g) was dissolved in distilled water and diluted to one litre.

Fehling's A solution:

Copper sulphate pentahydrate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (69.280g) was dissolved in distilled water and diluted to one litre. It was kept for a day before titration.

Fehling's B solution:

Sodium potassium tartrate ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{NaO}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (346.000g) and 100.000g of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were dissolved in distilled water and diluted to one litre. It was filtered through prepared Whatman filter papers.

Method:

Exactly 5.00 mL of Fehling's A solution was mixed with exactly 5.00 mL of Fehling's B solution for the standardization. It will react completely with 0.050 g of invert sugar added as 25mL dilute invert sugar solution. (2g/L).

Preparation of the test sample:

The homogeneous arishta sample was filtered and 2.000 g was accurately weighed to the nearest milligram. It was dissolved in distilled water and diluted to 200 mL in a calibrated flask. (arishta solution).

Exactly 50.00 mL of the arishta solution was diluted to 100 mL using distilled water. (diluted arishta solution).

Preliminary titration:

The total volume of the added reactants at the completion of the reduction titration must be 35 mL. This is made up by the addition of a suitable volume of water before the titration commences because a preliminary titration is necessary to establish the volume of water to be added to a given sample, to ensure the reduction is carried out at constant volume. This volume of water to be added is calculated by subtracting the volume of diluted arishta solution consumed in the preliminary titration (r mL) from 25 mL. Exactly 5 mL of fehling's solution A was pipetted into a 250mL erlenmeyer flask and approximately 5 mL of fehling's solution B was added. About 7 mL of distilled water, a little powdered pumice or other suitable anti bumping agents were added, followed by about 15.00 mL diluted arishta solution from a burette. The cold mixture was heated to boiling over a wire gauze, and moderate ebullition was maintained for two minutes. About one mL 0.2 per cent aqueous methylene blue solution was added whilst still boiling and the titration was completed within a total boiling time of 3 minutes, by repeated small additions of diluted arishta solution until the indicator is decolorized. It is the colour of the supernatant liquid that must be observed. The total volume of diluted arishta solution used was noted. (mL).

3.4.2.9.2. Determination of reducing sugar content

The amount of added water necessary to bring the total volume of the reactants at the completion of the titration to 35.00 mL by subtracting the preliminary titration (x mL) from 25.00 mL was calculated.

Exactly 5.00 mL fehling's solution A was pipetted into a 250-mL erlenmeyer flask and approximately 5.00 mL of fehling's solution B was added.

Calculated (25-x) mL distilled water, a little powdered pumice or other suitable antibumping agent was added and from a burette, all but 1.5 mL of the diluted arishta solution, volume determined in the preliminary titration. The cold mixture was heated to boiling over a wire gauze and moderate ebullition was maintained for two minutes. About 1.00 mL of 0.2 per cent methylene blue solution was added whilst still boiling and the titration was completed within a total boiling time of three minutes by repeated small additions of diluted arishta solution until the indicator is decolorized. The total volume of diluted arishta solution was noted. (y mL).

Titration were triplicated.

Calculation and expression of results -

$C = \frac{2000}{m \times y}$ where,

C = grams invert sugar per 100 g arishta (per cent); m = mass of honey sample taken; and y = volume of diluted arishta solution consumed in the determination in mL

3.4.2.10 Determination of apparent sucrose content

Principle of the method

Based on the Walker (1917) inversion method.

Reagents -

- Soxhlet modification of fehling's solution
- Standard invert sugar solution
- Hydrochloric acid, 6.34 N, aqueous.
- Sodium hydroxide solution, 5 N, aqueous.
- Methylene blue solution, 2 g/L (B.1.2.3). **Preliminary treatment of sample**

Procedure:

Preparation of test sample:

Prepare the arishta solution as in determination of reducing sugar content. Exactly 10.00 mL of this solution was diluted to 250.00 mL with distilled water, (diluted arishta solution).

Hydrolysis of the test sample:

The arishta solution (50.00 mL) was placed in a 100-mL graduated flask, together with 25.00 mL distilled water, the test sample was heated to 65 °C over a boiling water-bath. The flask was then removed from the water bath and 10.00 mL of 6.34 N hydrochloric acid was added. The solution was allowed to cool to room temperature for 15 minutes, and was neutralized with 5 N sodium hydroxide, using litmus paper as indicator, and the volume was adjusted to 100.00 mL. (diluted arishta solution).

Titration as in the determination of the reducing sugar content.

Calculation -

The percent invert sugar (grams invert sugar per 100 g honey) after inversion was calculated, using the same formula as for percent invert sugar before inversion in the determination of the reducing sugar content.

Apparent sucrose content =

(invert sugar content after inversion - invert sugar content before inversion) x 0.95 The

result is expressed as grams apparent sucrose per 100 g arishta.

3.4.2.11 Determination of alcohol content-

Alcohol content of arishta was determined using GC – FID method according to the internal protocol developed by the R&D, Link Natural Products (Pvt) Ltd, which is adopted by (Wang et al., 2003).

Materials and equipment:

- 1% acetonitrile solution
- 20 mL vials
- Filtered Nimba arishta samples

- Micro pipette

Methods:

Preparation of internal standard solution

Ten mL of acetonitrile was dispensed into 1000mL volumetric bottle and then distilled water was added to the 1000mL mark. This was the 1% (v/v) internal (acetonitrile) standard solution.

Quantitative ethanol determination:

Direct injected GC method-

Filtered Nimba arishta sample (1mL) was dispensed into an 20mL capped sample vial, and then 10 mL of 1% internal standard solution was added. After mixing, 1mL of the sample solution was injected directly into a GC with syringe.

GC conditions-

Agilent 7890B – GC-FID system was used. The flow rates of H₂ and air were set at 30 and 300 mL/min, respectively. Nitrogen in the flow rate of 1mL/min was used as the carrier gas. The GL sciences_1010-14747 separation column (intercap 624 : 30 m x 1.8 µm x 0.32 mm) was used. Oven temperature was set initially at 45°C for 2 minutes, and then increased to the final temperature of 225°C within 7 minutes at the rate of 45°C/min. Injection volume was limited to 0.5µl. Split-20:1 mode was selected.

3.4.2.12 Determination of total phenolic content

Phenolic content of arishta was determined as the internal protocol developed by the R&D, Link Natural Products (Pvt) Ltd, which is adopted by AOAC official method 952.03 – tannin in distilled liquors.

Preparation of Folin Denis reagent:

Exactly 12.500 g of sodium tungstate and 2.500 g of phosphomolybdic acid and 6.25 mL of phosphoric acid was added and mixed with 100 mL of water.

It was refluxed for 2 hours and let to cool to room temperature and diluted to 125 mL.

Preparation of saturated Sodium carbonate:

Anhydrous sodium carbonate (35.000g) was mixed with water (100.00mL) and dissolved at 7080°C. It was kept overnight and filtered through filter paper (Whatman NO:01).

Preparation of tannic acid solutions:

- Stock solution (500 ppm):

Exactly 0.125 g of purified tannic acid was taken in to 250 mL amber coloured volumetric flask. It was dissolved well and topped up to the mark with distilled water.

- 10 ppm tannic acid solution:

2 mL of stock solution was dissolved with distilled water in a 100 mL amber coloured volumetric flask.

- 20 ppm tannic acid solution:

4mL of stock solution was dissolved with distilled water in 100 mL amber coloured volumetric flask.

- 30 ppm tannic acid solution:

6 mL of stock solution was dissolved with distilled water in a 100 mL amber coloured volumetric flask.

- 40 ppm tannic acid solution:

8 mL of stock solution was dissolved with distilled water in a 100 mL amber coloured volumetric flask.

- 50 ppm tannic acid solution:

10 mL of stock solution was dissolved with distilled water in a 100 mL amber coloured volumetric flask.

- Blank solution:

10 mL of saturated sodium carbonate and 5 mL Folin Denis reagents were taken in to a 100mL volumetric flask and marked up with distilled water.

Plotting the standard curve -

10.0 mL of testing solution was taken into a 100 mL volumetric flask. 10 mL of saturated sodium carbonate and 5 mL Folin Denis reagents were added. It was marked up with distilled water and mixed well.

Absorbance was determined at 760 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer, after 30 minutes.

Test method:

Exactly 1.000g of the filtered arishta sample was added into a 100 mL volumetric flask. Then make up the mark using distilled water.

Into a 100mL volumetric flask, 10.00 mL of the diluted sample was pipetted and 5.00 mL of Folin Denis reagent and 10.00mL of saturated Na₂CO₃ solution were added respectively.

It was mixed well, and the absorbance was determined after 30 minutes at 760nm using the blank solution.

3.4.2.13 Determination of flavonoid content –

Flavonoid content of arishta was determined as the internal protocol developed by the R&D, Link Natural Products (Pvt) Ltd, which is adopted by (Shraim et al., 2021)

Calibration plot of quercetin standard

The standard solution of quercetin was prepared by using 80% methanol solution (250 mL (An amount of 0.0062 g of Quercetin was dissolved in a 25.00 mL volumetric flask with 80% methanol solution (v/v)).

Aliquots of 0.50 mL, 0.75 mL, 1.00 mL, 1.25 mL, and 1.50 mL were pipetted out and transferred into 10.00 mL volumetric flasks separately and distilled water was added to make 4 mL.

An amount of 0.30 mL of NaNO₂ solution was added and mixed well. (NaNO₂ solution was prepared by dissolving 5.0000g of NaNO₂ in 100 mL of distilled water)

An amount of 3.00 mL of AlCl₃ solution was added 5 min later. (AlCl₃ solution was prepared by dissolving 1.000g of AlCl₃ in 100.00 mL of distilled water)

After 6 minutes, 2.0 mL of 1M NaOH solution was added. And the total volume was made upto 10 mL with distilled water and solution was mixed well. Then absorbance of solution was measured against a blank at 510nm with a UV-visible spectrophotometer 1min later.

Blank solution- An amount of 1.0 mL of 80% methanol solution (v/v) was placed in a 10.0 mL volumetric flask and distilled water was added to make 4 mL. Then 0.30 mL of NaNO₂ solution, 3.0 mL of AlCl₃ solution and 2.0 mL of 1 M NaOH solution were added according to proper time duration (mentioned). The total volume was made up to 10 mL, with distilled water.

The calibration plot was drawn using absorbance reading vs concentration of solutions.

Test method:

An amount of 0.20 mL of the filtered arishta sample was transferred to a 10mL volumetric flask and distilled water was added to make 4.00mL.

An amount of 0.30 mL of NaNO₂ was added and mixed well. (NaNO₂ solution was prepared by dissolving 5g of NaNO₂ in 100 mL of distilled water)

An amount of 3.0 mL of AlCl₃ solution was added 5 min later. (AlCl₃ solution was prepared by dissolving 1g of AlCl₃ in 100 mL of distilled water)

After 6 minutes, 2.0 mL of 1 M NaOH solution was added.

The total volume was made up to 10 mL with distilled water and solution was mixed well after 1 minute.

The absorbance was measured immediately at 510 nm using 80% blank solution.

3.4.2.14 Determination of proanthocyanidin content:

A modified butanol/acid assay method was adopted by (Shay et al., 2017,Pormrt, 1986).

Determination of the moisture content of the dried extract-

Filtered arishta sample (50mL) was concentrated in rota vapor (BUCHI -Labortechnik AG type

R-100) at temperature 55°C and pressure not below 40 mbar. A known weight of the dried extract (5g) was analysed for moisture content using the Dean and Stark method (method described in European pharmacopoeia 8.0 - 2.8.23).

Sample preparation for the analysis of proanthocyanidin content-

The weight of the sample of the dried extract to be used for the analysis was calculated as to contain 800mg of the dried weight. Calculated weight was added to a centrifuge tube, and it was dissolved in 5.00mL of methanol, vortexed briefly. Exactly 25.00 mL of 60% aqueous acetone was added and was taken to vortex again.

It was sonicated for 10 minutes and extracted for a further 57 minutes at room temperature. The tube was centrifuged for 5 minutes at 4000 rpm in the centrifuge (model-BKC-TH18) and the supernatants were removed.

Reagents -

1. Butanol/HCl solution (95:5 (v/v))
2. $\text{NH}_4\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 2M HCl

Blank solution :

To a 20mL glass vial, 250 μ l of methanol, 750 μ l of acetone, 500 μ l of distilled water, 9.0mL of 95% solution of butanol/HCl and 300 μ l of $\text{NH}_4\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 2M HCl were added.

Determination of the proanthocyanidin content –

To a 20mL glass vial, 1.5 mL aliquot of the supernatant, 9mL of a 95% solution of butanol/HCl were added. Then 0.3 mL of a solution of $\text{NH}_4\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 2M HCl was added. It was incubated for 40 minutes at 95 °C and then, the absorbance was measured at 550nm using the UV-Vis Spectrophotometer.

3.4.2.15 Determination of DPPH radical scavenging activity:

DPPH radical scavenging activity of Nimba arishta was determined according to the method described in (Annadurai & Soundarapandian, 2018)

Materials, Apparatus and equipment:

- Distilled water
- 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH)
- Methanol
- Micro tubes and caps
- Test tubes and micro tubes rack
- Micro pipettes
- Volumetric flasks
- Vortex mixer
- Test tubes
- UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Agilent 8453)

Preparation of Nimba Arishta dilution series for determination of the antioxidant activity:

About 20.00mL of arishta sample was centrifuged at 3000rpm for 5 minutes and filtered to obtain supernatant.

Then ten-fold dilution series of the samples were prepared using distilled water. Finally, 6 dilution series were prepared.

Preparation of 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) solution:

To prepare the DPPH solution, 4mg of DPPH was measured and transferred into the 100mL volumetric flasks. Then it was dissolved by 80% methanol. Solution was properly mixed and topped up with 80% methanol. The flask was covered with aluminium foil and kept for 1 hour in dark place.

Testing method for antioxidant activity:

As the control sample, 0.5mL of distilled water and 2.5mL of DPPH solution was transferred into a micro tube. Then 0.5mL of diluted samples and 2.5mL of DPPH solution were added to other micro tubes (1:5) and subsequently shaken. Tubes were kept at 27 °C for 20 minutes in dark. Then, the tubes were vortexed, and the absorbance was recorded at 517nm using UV-Vis

Spectrophotometer. All tubes were prepared in this way and closed with caps and placed in the aluminium foil covered rack and duplicated the procedure.

DPPH scavenging effects were calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ of DPPH radical scavenging effect} = [(A_0 - A) / A_0 \times 100]$$

Where A_0 denotes absorbance of the control; A denotes absorbance in the presence of samples.

IC50 values were calculated from the slope of the standard graph using 'y = mx + c' formula for every case.

L-ascorbic acid was the standard used and the standard curve was plotted.

Preparation of ascorbic acid solutions:

- Stock solution (100 μ g/ml):

Exactly 5.000g of ascorbic acid was taken in to 50 mL volumetric flask. It was dissolved well and topped up to the mark with distilled water.

- 5 ppm ascorbic acid solution:

500 μ L of stock solution was dissolved with distilled water in 10 mL volumetric flask.

- 15 ppm ascorbic acid solution:

1.5mL of stock solution was dissolved with distilled water in 10 mL volumetric flask.

- 25 ppm ascorbic acid solution:

2.5mL of stock solution was dissolved with distilled water in 10 mL volumetric flask.

- 35 ppm ascorbic acid solution:

3.5mL of stock solution was dissolved with distilled water in 10 mL volumetric flask.

- 45 ppm ascorbic acid solution:

4.5mL of stock solution was dissolved with distilled water in 10 mL volumetric flask.

Then 0.5mL of diluted ascorbic acid samples and 2.5mL of DPPH solution were added to other micro tubes (1:5) and subsequently shaken. Tubes were kept at 27 °C for 20 minutes in dark. Then, the tubes were vortexed, and the absorbance was recorded at 517nm using UV-Vis Spectrophotometer.

Chapter 04

Results and Discussion

4.1 Statistical analysis:

The results were represented as mean \pm standard deviation of mean (SD) of three independent experiments. Statistical analyses were performed using one-way analysis of variance (Tukey's test at $p < 0.05$) by employing the statistical software Minitab (version - Minitab® 19.2020.1).

4.2 Physicochemical properties of Nimba arishta samples –

Results of all the physicochemical properties were statistically analyzed using one way ANOVA with 95% confidence level ($\alpha=0.05$).

Two hypotheses were used for each parameter.

H_0 – All means are equal.

H_1 – Not all means are equal.

Decision rule: if p value $< \alpha$, reject H_0

4.2.1 pH

Table 4.1 - Results of pH for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	pH	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence		
A	3.64 \pm 0.04	A		
B	3.11 \pm 0.01		B	
C	3.10 \pm 0.03		B	
D	3.01 \pm 0.01			C
E	3.14 \pm 0.04		B	

F	3.07±0.03		B	C
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Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=3)

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Figure 4.1 -Interval plot of pH versus different brands

According to the results of one-way ANOVA,

$P=0.00$, therefore H_0 is rejected. It can be concluded that there are significant differences among different brands of Nimba arishta in terms of the pH value.

The observed pH values are found within the range of 3.01 and 3.64 which are acidic values. Sample A generally has the lowest acidity, while Sample D tends to have the highest acidity. The remaining brands (B, C, E, and F) have varying degrees of acidity that are significantly lower than Sample D.

During fermentation, the microorganisms, bacteria and yeast produce various organic acids as by products. The accumulation of organic acids, such as lactic acid, acetic acid, or citric acid, can contribute to the acidity observed in arishta.

Arishta formulation contains ingredients with polyphenolic compounds such as hydrolysable tannins and condensed tannins. While making the decoction, those polyphenolic compounds are

hydrolyzed and phenolic acids such as gallic acid, ellagic acid and caffeic acid etc. are produced, results in lowering the pH of the decoction. Therefore, sample A with highest pH can be considered to contain lesser amount of hydrolysable tannins compared to the rest of the samples.

The fruits of *P. emblica* is acidic in nature and these acidic ingredients can contribute to the overall acidity of the arishta if they were added as given in the formula 2 of Nimba arishta in Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia.

The acidic pH can help create an environment conducive to the growth of desired microorganisms and inhibit the growth of undesirable ones, thus helping to extend the shelf life of the arishta. According to Chinky et al., 2021 this acidic pH range is an indicative of low bacterial count, while neutral or alkaline pH levels may suggest a higher level of contamination in the herbal preparation.

The pH of Nimba arishtas in a previous study ranged from 3.2 to 3.6 (Kroes et al., 1989), which slightly changes to the pH range observed in the present results.

4.2.2 Brix value / Total Soluble Solids (TSS)

Table 4.2 - Results of brix for different brands of Nimba Arishta –

Sample	Brix %	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence			
A	25.06±0.15				D
B	29.23±0.25		B		
C	41.00±0.50	A			
D	27.40±0.40			C	
E	30.10±0.10		B		
F	27.5±0.50			C	

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=3)

According to the results of one-way ANOVA,

$P=0.00$, therefore, H_0 is rejected. It can be concluded that there are significant differences among different brands of Nimba arishta in terms of the values of brix.

Figure 4.2 -interval plot of brix value versus different brands

The analysis of Brix values among the six different arishta brands demonstrates significant differences in their mean values. Brands in group A (sample C) have the highest brix value, while brands in group D (sample A) have the lowest brix value. Brands in groups B and C fall in between.

Degrees Brix is the content of sugar in an aqueous solution of sugar. 1 g of sucrose dissolved in 100 g of water yields one degree Brix. The TSS (brix) was determined in a small sample of arishta using Abbe refractometer. These statistical findings suggest that there are variations in the brix values among the different arishta brands, indicating differences in their composition or manufacturing processes. However, one common component of arishta is sugar, which contributes to sweetness and acts as a source of fermentable carbohydrates for the fermentation process.

In traditional arishta preparations, sweeteners such as sugar, jaggery or honey are commonly used. These sweeteners contain various forms of sugar, such as sucrose, glucose, and fructose, which are soluble in water and contribute to the overall soluble solids content of the arishta.

It's important to note that the specific composition and concentration of soluble solids in arishta can differ based on the individual recipe and the desired therapeutic effects. The concentration of soluble solids, including sugars, in arishta can vary depending on factors such as the amount of sweetener added and the duration of fermentation. Those samples with higher brix values were found to contain lesser ethanol content due to the incomplete fermentation.

4.2.3 Refractive index

Table 4.3 - Results of refractive index for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Refractive index	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence				
A	1.3725±0.0005					E
B	1.3798±0.0002			C		
C	1.4019±0.0001	A				
D	1.3769±0.0003				D	
E	1.3814±0.0004		B			
F	1.3767±0.0003				D	

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=3)

According to the results of one-way ANOVA,

The "sample" factor has 5 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.000, which means there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis. It suggests that the means of refractive index values are not equal across all brands.

Figure 4.3 -Interval plot of refractive index versus different brands

Refractive index was measured using the Abbe refractometer. This instrument measures the refractive index, which indicates the degree of deviation of a light beam as it passes through the arishta sample. The refractive index can be influenced by the composition and concentration of solutes present in the sample. Here, the refractive index value is found within a narrow range of 1.37 and 1.40. The Tukey pairwise comparisons further elucidate the specific differences between the brands. Sample C exhibits a significantly higher refractive index compared to all other brands, indicating that it likely contains a different concentration of solutes or unique chemical components affecting its optical properties.

In certain cases, the refractive index can be used as an indicator of quality or adulteration in beverages. Deviations from expected refractive index values may indicate the presence of contaminants, dilution, or improper manufacturing processes. The refractive index can serve as a quality control parameter for consistency in the production of arishtas. Establishing a reference range of refractive index values for a specific decoction formulation can help identify any deviations or variations in subsequent batches, indicating potential issues in the fermentation process or ingredient quality.

4.2.4 Specific gravity

Table 4.4- Results of specific gravity for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Specific gravity	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence					
A	1.0684±0.0004						F
B	1.0965±0.0005			C			
C	1.1632±0.0005	A					
D	1.0894±0.0004				D		
E	1.1048±0.0007		B				
F	1.0864±0.0004					E	

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=3)

Figure 3.4 -Interval plot of specific gravity versus different brands According to the results of one-way ANOVA,

$P=0.00$, therefore, H_0 is rejected. It can be concluded that there are significant differences among different brands of Nimba arishta in terms of the values of specific gravity.

The analysis of specific gravity among different brands of Nimba arishta revealed significant differences in the means of specific gravity values. This implies that the specific gravity, which is a measure of the density of the liquid, varies significantly across the different brands. Higher specific gravity values may indicate a higher concentration of dissolved substances or herbal extracts in the fermented decoction. Sample C exhibits a significantly higher specific gravity compared to all other brands,

This suggests that the specific gravity of arishtas is influenced by factors such as the selection and proportions of herbs used, the fermentation process, and the manufacturing techniques employed by different brands.

4.2.5 - Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

Table 4.5 - Results of total dissolved solids for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Total Dissolved Solids (g/ml)	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence				
A	0.1993±0.0012					E
B	0.2522±0.0050			C		
C	0.4107±0.0023	A				
D	0.2534±0.0030			C		
E	0.2806±0.0013		B			
F	0.2387±0.0042				D	

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=3)

Figure 4.5 -Interval plot of TDS versus different brands

There is a p-value of 0.000, which means there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis. It suggests that the means of values of total dissolved solids are not equal across all brands.

The null hypothesis, which states that all means are equal, was rejected with a high level of significance ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that there are significant differences in the mean total dissolved solids among the brands. According to the Tukey simultaneous tests, significant differences were found between most of the pairwise comparisons. Sample C consistently showed the highest mean total dissolved solids, while Sample A had the lowest mean. The other brands exhibited intermediate levels of total dissolved solids.

The total solid means the residue obtained when the specific amount of the preparation is dried to constant weight under specified conditions. The variations in TDS content suggest differences in the composition and processing methods among the brands.

Additionally, water-soluble components like herbal extracts or secondary metabolites derived from the herbs used in the formulation such as organic acids, amino acids, soluble pectins, etc. may also contribute to the overall dissolved solids content of arishta.

Elevated levels of TDS may suggest the presence of contaminants such as minerals, salts, heavy metals, organic compounds, or other dissolved substances. Controlling and maintaining appropriate TDS levels can help enhance the sensory qualities and consumer

acceptance of beverages. High TDS levels can impact the solubility and precipitation of certain components, leading to sedimentation or changes in appearance over time. Monitoring and controlling TDS levels helps maintain the desired product stability and extend the shelf life of the beverage.

4.2.6 Total Ash content -

Table 4.6 - Results of total ash content for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Total ash content (w/w%)	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence			
A	0.1070±0.0014				D
B	0.3378±0.0455			C	
C	0.2709±0.0005			C	
D	0.0971±0.0045				D
E	1.5548±0.0011	A			
F	0.9607±0.0010		B		

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=2)

The one-way ANOVA results indicate a significant difference in the total ash content among the brands ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that all means are equal is rejected, suggesting that at least one brand has a different total ash content compared to the others.

Figure 4.6 -Interval plot of total ash versus different brands

Sample E has the highest total ash content and is significantly different from all other brands. Sample A and Sample D have the lowest total ash content, and they are not significantly different from each other.

The significance of the total ash (%) parameter in the analysis of arishta, lies in its ability to provide information about the mineral content of the product. Total ash refers to the inorganic residue left behind after the complete combustion of organic matter. Thus, the ash content serves as a criterion for assessing the identity and purity of crude drugs.

4.2.7 Acid insoluble ash content –

Table 4.7 - Results of acid insoluble ash content for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Acid insoluble ash content (w/w%)	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence
A	0.0399±0.0013	A
B	0.0135±0.0050	A
C	0.0481±0.0099	A
D	0.0131±0.0041	A
E	0.0406±0.0288	A
F	0.0571±0.0306	A

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=2)

The p-value obtained from the ANOVA test is 0.199, which is greater than the significance level. Therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is not enough evidence to suggest that the means of acid insoluble ash differ among the brands.

This suggests that the brands do not vary in terms of their acid insoluble ash content. The presence of only a little amount of acid insoluble ash in these arishta samples indicates the absence of impurities resembling silica in the drug. Low acid insoluble ash content in all samples indicates high purity of the drugs with lesser contaminations during the manufacturing process.

Figure 4.7 -Interval plot of acid insoluble ash versus different brands

4.2.8 Water soluble ash content –

Table 4.8 - Results of water-soluble ash content for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Water soluble ash content (w/w%)	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence		
A	0.0580±0.0113	A	B	
B	0.0040±0.0028			C
C	0.0878±0.0108	A		
D	0.0444±0.0076		B	
E	0.0280±0.0113		B	C
F	0.0899±0.0127	A		

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=2)

The p-value obtained for the 'Brands' factor is 0.001, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis of equal means and conclude that there is a significant difference in water-soluble ash content among the Nimba arishta brands.

Figure 4.8 -Interval plot of water-soluble ash versus different brands

Sample F has the highest mean (0.08990), followed closely by Sample C (0.08775). Sample A (0.05800) and Sample D (0.04440) have relatively lower means. Sample B (0.00400) and Sample E (0.02800) have the lowest means.

The water-soluble ash content of a herbal drug is an indicator of the amount of inorganic substances present in the drug that are soluble in water. It provides information about the level of mineral matter present in the herbal drug. Thus, the water-soluble ash content helps assess the quality of the herbal drug by measuring the amount of these water-soluble inorganic content.

4.2.9 Reducing sugar content –

Table 4.9 - Results of Reducing sugar content for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Reducing sugar content (g invert sugar per 100g sample)	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence			
A	15.75±0.27				D
B	24.54±0.06		B		
C	34.24±0.48	A			
D	21.57±0.16			C	
E	24.93±0.06		B		
F	21.03±0.05			C	

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=3)

The p-value obtained (0.000) is less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis that all means are equal.

The tukey simultaneous tests for differences of means provide specific comparisons between brands. In a similar study conducted to investigate the reducing sugar content in Nimba arishta, predominantly glucose and fructose were found. Therefore, it can be concluded that glucose and fructose are the types of reducing sugars found in these samples.

Even though it was given in the formulations that only sugar was added as the substrate, there are instances that bees honey was added to the decoction. Different quality bees honey is often adulterated with glucose, fructose, sucrose and corn syrup (Tennakoon, 2002) results in variations in sugar profile of different arishta samples. It was found from this study, that the total reducing sugar concentration ranged from 15.7 to 34.2 % (w/w) among these Nimba arishta samples. The amount of total reducing sugar present in samples can be less due to more sugar being added in order to mask the sour taste or profit gain. The results of the reducing sugar content also shows that the sample with higher reducing sugar content contains unfermented sugars since it contains lesser ethanol content.

Figure 4.9 -Interval plot of reducing sugar content versus different brands

4.2.10 Apparent sucrose content (g per 100g sample)-

Table 4.10 - Results of apparent sucrose content for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Apparent sucrose content (g per 100g sample)	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence			
A	1.07±0.11				D
B	0.69±0.21				D
C	1.43±0.03				D
D	2.62±0.39			C	
E	7.69±0.47	A			
F	3.98±0.20		B		

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=3)

The ANOVA results indicate that there are significant differences in the apparent sucrose content among the different brands of Nimba arishta. The p-value is reported as 0.000, which is below the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, providing strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis that all means are equal.

Figure 4.10 -Interval plot of apparent sucrose content versus different brands

Sample E has the highest apparent sucrose content and is significantly different from all other brands. Sample C, Sample A, and Sample B have lower apparent sucrose content and are significantly different from Sample D, Sample E, and Sample F.

Overall, these results suggest that there are notable variations in the apparent sucrose content among different brands of Nimba arishta. Some brands have significantly higher sucrose content compared to others, which may impact their perceived sweetness and flavor. These variations reflect the diverse carbohydrate metabolism during fermentation, leading to different sugar profiles in the arishta products.

In a similar study on the analysis of sucrose in Nimba arishta, a minor amount of sucrose had been detected only in several samples of arishta. But here, a small amount of sucrose content was found in each sample studied.

These results show that sucrose is hydrolyzed during the process of fermentation. The variations in the quantity of sugar added initially may directly cause to these changes. These findings can be valuable for manufacturers aiming to differentiate their products based on sucrose content.

4.2.11 Ethanol content -

Table 4.11 - Results of ethanol content for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Ethanol content (V/V %)	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence				
A	10.4±0.141	A				
B	9.4±0.00			C		
C	7.65±0.0.07					E
D	8.8±0.141				D	
E	8.6±0.00				D	
F	9.85±0.07		B			

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=3)

The statistical results indicate that there are significant differences in the ethanol content among the different brands of Nimba Arishta.

As per the Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India, the recommended range for self-generated alcohol content in arishtas is between 5% and 10%. The present investigation reveals that all preparations except sample A contain acceptable levels of alcohol. Sample A has shown the highest amount of alcohol content. In a previous investigation on Nimba arishta, the ethanol content has been found within the range of 6-10%, which does not show a vast variation to the present results. (Kroes et al., 1989). These variations in alcohol content indicate differences in the fermentation process, duration, or ingredients used in the production of the arishta. The alcohol content provides insights into the extent of fermentation and the potential bioactive properties associated with alcohol-soluble compounds.

Due to its acidic, organic nature and solubility in water, alcohol aids in extracting both watersoluble and insoluble components from plant materials, potentially altering the characteristics of the samples.

According to (Thomas et al. 2016), this problem of varying amounts of alcohol content in arishta can be overcome by adopting the fermentation method employed in brewing of wine.

Figure 4.11 -Interval plot of ethanol content versus different brands

4.2.12 Total phenolic content – (TPC)

Table 4.12 - Results of total polyphenolic content for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Total phenolic content (TAE in mg per g of sample)	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence				
A	1.7275 ±0.0262					E
B	9.036±0.332		B			
C	8.255±0.186			C		
D	5.8545±0.0233				D	
E	9.0630±0.0735	A	B			
F	9.727±0.161	A				

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=2)

The p-value is highly significant ($p = 0.000$), indicating that there are significant differences in the means of total polyphenolic content among the different brands of Nimba arishta. The null hypothesis of equal means is rejected. The mean values of total polyphenolic content vary among the different brands.

Brands in different groups have significantly different total phenolic content. This means that the different brands have varying levels of phenolic compounds. All comparisons between Sample A and the other brands (B, C, D, E, F) are highly significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that Sample A has significantly lower total phenolic content compared to the other brands.

Sample F stands out with the highest mean value of 9.727 mg/g, indicating that it has the highest concentration of phenolic compounds among all the brands.

Figure 4.12 -Interval plot of TPC versus different brands

When arranging the raw materials used for the preparation of Nimba arishta in descending order of their TPC, the correct order is as follows: *T. chebula*, *T. bellerica*, *P. emblica* and bark of *A. indica* respectively.

Tannin content in the bark of *A. indica* is lower compared to the leaves. It contains both hydrolysable tannins and CT in least amounts compared to that of ingredients mentioned in the formula 2 (figure 2.1). Therefore, sample A with the least TPC can be considered to prepare according to formula 1 (figure 2.1). The rest of the samples with considerably higher amounts of TPC can be considered to have formula 2.

4.2.13 Total flavonoid content – (TFC)

Table 4.13 - Results of total flavonoid content for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Total flavonoid content (QE in mg per g of sample)	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence				
A	1.24105 ±0.01308					E
B	3.2151±0.0417	A				
C	2.0306±0.0847			C		
D	1.6043±0.0499				D	
E	2.1004±0.00057			C		
F	2.9279±0.0339		B			

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=2)

The analysis of variance indicates significant differences in the total flavonoid content among the brands of Nimba arishta ($p = 0.000$). This suggests that the different brands have varying levels of flavonoid compounds.

Sample B has the highest mean value of 3.2151 mg/g, indicating that it has the highest concentration of flavonoids and sample A has the lowest mean value of 1.24105 mg/g, suggesting it has the lowest concentration of flavonoids compared to the other brands.

Total flavonoid content of arishta was determined using the aluminium chloride method. Total flavonoid content of samples was measured as quercetin equivalents. Quercetin is a plant pigment which represents aglycone form of a number of flavonoid glycosides that possess antioxidant activity.

It is given that sample A is manufactured using formula 1 (figure 2.2) which uses the decoction made only from the bark of *A. indica* and other plant materials mentioned in formula 2 are not used. (B. H. Kroes et al., 1993). It is evident from the vast variation shown in the bioactive components of sample A, that its composition is different from that of other samples because it contains the least TPC and TFC.

Figure 4.13 -Interval plot of TFC versus different brands

4.2.14 Proanthocyanidin (CT) content –

Table 4.14 - Results of Proanthocyanidin content for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Proanthocyanidin content (AU)	Grouping using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence				
A	0.13490±0.00127	A				
B	0.08970±0.00523			C		
C	0.03748±0.00153				D	
D	0.11488±0.0027		B			
E	0.05054±0.00191				D	
F	0.01027±0.00675					E

Data represented as mean values ± S.D. (n=2)

The analysis of variance reveals a significant difference in the CT content among the brands of arishta ($p = 0.000$). This indicates that the various brands have distinct levels of CT compounds.

Sample A has the highest mean CT content of 0.1349 AU and sample F has the lowest mean CT content of 0.01027 AU. Within each group, the brands do not exhibit significant differences in CT content. However, there are notable disparities between the groups.

It can be considered that the content of CT is an indication of the variations of raw material quality such as immature bark. Since a reference was not available, the CT content was quantitatively compared based on the absorbance values.

One advantage of the butanol-HCl method is that it enables the direct quantification of all fractions of CT, including water-soluble, organic solvent-extractable, and unextractable (functionally insoluble) CT. (Shay et al. 2017).

Due to the absence of a suitable standard such as cyanidin chloride, absorbances of the samples only were comparatively analysed. The absorbance was read at 550nm after a red coloration was developed in the samples. The choice of standards is an unresolved problem due to the heterogeneity of CT and the lack of appropriate standards for the quantification of CT. A ratio of acid-butanol to sample medium of 6:1 was used initially. When the ratio of reagent to sample was decreased to 2:1, the colour yield increased. Since hydrolysable tannins do not react in this assay, it can be assumed that this absorbance value is an indication of CT.

Research studies have identified and analyzed the tannin content of *A. indica* extracts, confirming the presence of CT in significant amounts. *T. chebula* contains both hydrolyzable and CT and is known to have a relatively higher tannin content along with *T. bellerica* and *P. emblica*. Therefore, it can be concluded that the rest of the samples except sample A are made using formula 2 which includes plant ingredients containing more TPC and TFC.

Figure 4.14 -Interval plot of CT versus different brands

4.3 Antioxidant activity of Nimba arishta –

The antioxidant activity of phenolic compounds is mainly due to their properties, which allow them to act as reducing agents, hydrogen donors and metal chelators. (Megalhaes et al., 2008). The antioxidant activity was evaluated in the study by using in vitro DPPH assay.

4.3.1 DPPH Radical scavenging activity (IC₅₀)–

Table 4.15 - Results of free radical scavenging activity for different brands of Nimba Arishta

Sample	Free radical scavenging activity (I ₅₀)–(μg/ml)
A	47.68
B	48.04
C	40.97
D	42.98
E	38.69
F	35.76

Nimba arishta samples upon treatment with DPPH, react with methanol and yield purple DPPH radicals. The antioxidant molecules scavenge DPPH radicals and convert them to a yellow colour.

Nimba arishta was found to be potent DPPH-free radical scavenger because there is high amount of phenolics, flavonoids and proanthocyanidin compounds with better antioxidant properties. It is shown that the IC₅₀ value for different brands of Nimba arishta are found in a narrow range. However, it's important to note that further analysis or additional data may be necessary to draw definitive conclusions.

Eventhough the variations were observed in the contents of phenolics, flavonoids and CT, the radical scavenging potential was found to be approximately same. This can be due to the lack of sensitivity of the method employed. The DPPH assay determines only the hydrophilic antioxidants in arishta samples and lipophilic antioxidants are not measured. (Re et al., 1999). This is also can be a reason for these results because the lipophilic antioxidants may not be detected with DPPH. Some of the lipophilic antioxidants found in *A. indica* include nimbidin, nimbin, and gedunin. Gallic acid and ellagic acid derivatives found in *P. emblica* are also lipophilic antioxidants that may be undermined in DPPH assay.

Ascorbic acid was used as the control because it is an excellent electron donor because of its low standard 1-electron reduction potential, allowing for the conversion of the relatively stable semi-dehydroascorbic acid to ascorbic acid. (Lee et al., 2004). It was shown from the standard curve of ascorbic acid, that its IC₅₀ value is 29.7784 ug/ml. In comparison to the IC₅₀ values, it is clearly shown that the IC₅₀ values of all the different brands are higher than that of ascorbic acid. IC₅₀ value is inversely proportional to the antioxidant activity. All these samples were found to have lower antioxidant potential than that of the control. Since the IC₅₀ values of the samples are not much higher than the control, there's a considerable amount of antioxidants in Nimba arishta samples.

The relationship between polyphenols and antioxidant properties can be thoroughly demonstrated. (Hussain et al., 2016).

Samples E and F exhibit high levels of phenolic content, which is strongly associated with their antioxidant activity. This is evident from their low IC₅₀ values, indicating that their antioxidant activity surpasses that of the other samples. This highlights their superior ability to scavenge free radicals and mitigate oxidative damage compared to the other samples.

According to a study conducted by (Hur et al., 2014), it has been discovered that fermentation plays a crucial role in increasing the levels of phenols and flavonoids in plant extracts. This increase is beneficial as there is a well-established positive correlation between polyphenols and the antioxidant activities of herbs. It's important to note that the strength of the correlation can vary depending on the specific compounds and their concentrations within the herbal preparation. The enhanced antioxidant activity observed in these samples can be attributed to the process of fermentation.

There were some variations observed in absorbances of sample. This could be due to the several factors, such as low pH of sample, environmental conditions as well as human errors during the experiment.

In this case some absorbances were not linear. This could be due to the presence of high-water content in arishta. There was some evidence that showed DPPH reactions are highly sensitive to reaction medium, pH and oxygen. Water disrupts the binding and facilitates H atom transfer, so when there is water in the reaction medium, any test compounds with H atom transfer capabilities increase their reaction rate. Similarly, electron transfer is pH dependent. Therefore, low pH in arishta may also affect the absorbance. The results described by (Pekal & Pyrzyńska, 2015) showed that certain metal ions occurring in plants affect the results obtained in DPPH assay.

Therefore, it could be a reason that affected the DPPH assay results of Nimba arishta.

4.4 Sensory evaluation

In the present study an attempt was made to develop a sensory based quality control tool to differentiate the market samples of Nimba arishta on the basis of odour and taste. Sensory evaluation was conducted among the six different brands of Nimba arishta. Samples were subjected to sensory evaluation using the internal panel of Link Natural Products (Pvt) Ltd. The sensory panel comprised of ten highly trained members who had undergone extensive sensory training. Seven attributes were evaluated: herbaceous odour, medicinal odour, aromatic odour, sour taste, sweet taste, bitter taste and astringent taste. In this study, the assessment focused on the sensory attributes of odour and taste. These attributes encompass both the olfactory and gustatory sensations experienced during tasting. Being all the samples were identical in colour, it was not included as an evaluation attribute in the present study. The sensory properties were presented on a five-point hedonic scale and quantitative descriptive analysis (QDA) was the method employed.

The data obtained from the sensory evaluation was analyzed by using Minitab software (version - Minitab® 19.2020.1) with Kruskal-Wallis test method under non-parametric analysis to determine if there are significant differences among three or more independent groups in terms of their medians. In the context of analyzing sensory results, the Kruskal-Wallis test can be employed to examine if there are significant differences in the perception of sensory attributes among different samples. The average point number for each of the attributes was calculated.

Table 4.16 - Mean ranks of sensory evaluation of different brands of Nimba arishta

Sample	herbaceous odour	medicinal odour	aromatic odour	sour taste	sweet taste	bitter taste	astringent taste
A	25.4	30.7	31.1	22.4	38.0	18.9	27.2

B	34.1	28.6	31.9	28.4	39.4	30.7	25.1
C	34.1	28.6	31.9	28.4	39.4	28.1	28.1
D	26.0	27.8	33.3	30.5	32.1	22.8	30.3
E	29.3	31.9	22.4	33.5	18.1	37.9	38.2
F	34.0	35.5	32.5	39.8	16.1	44.6	34.0
Pvalue	0.695	0.905	0.718	0.261	0.001	0.008	0.537

Data represent as mean ranks (n=10)

Two hypotheses were used. Where, H_0 –

medians are equal for the six samples.

H_1 – medians are not equal for the six samples.

Seven sensory attributes were evaluated by comparing the calculated H value with the value obtained from the chi-square table (H_{table}) and thereby determined the significant difference among each and every attribute.

4.4.1 Herbaceous odour

$H_{cal} = 3.03$

When degree of freedom (DF) = 5,

$\chi^2 = 11.070$ (from chi-square table)

Therefore;

$H_{cal} < H_{table}$, there is no enough evidence to reject H_0 ; can conclude that there is no significance difference among the herbaceous odour of the samples.

4.4.2 Medicinal odour

$H_{cal} = 1.57$

When degree of freedom (DF) = 5,

$$\chi^2 = 11.070 \text{ (from chi-square table)}$$

Therefore;

$H_{\text{cal}} < H_{\text{table}}$, there is no enough evidence to reject H_0 ; can conclude that there is no significant difference among the medicinal odour of the samples.

4.4.3 Aromatic odour

$$H_{\text{cal}} = 2.88$$

When degree of freedom (DF) = 5,

$$\chi^2 = 11.070 \text{ (from chi-square table)}$$

Therefore;

$H_{\text{cal}} < H_{\text{table}}$, there is no enough evidence to reject H_0 ; can conclude that there is no significant difference among the aromatic odour of the samples.

4.4.4 Sour taste

$$H_{\text{cal}} = 6.49$$

When degree of freedom (DF) = 5,

$$\chi^2 = 11.070 \text{ (from chi-square table)}$$

Therefore;

$H_{\text{cal}} < H_{\text{table}}$, there is no enough evidence to reject H_0 ; can conclude that there is no significant difference among the sour taste of the samples.

4.4.5 Sweet taste

$$H_{\text{cal}} = 21.17$$

When degree of freedom (DF) = 5,

$$\chi^2 = 11.070 \text{ (from chi-square table)}$$

Therefore;

$H_{\text{cal}} > H_{\text{table}}$, there is enough evidence to reject H_0 ; can conclude that there is a significance difference among the sweet taste of the samples.

4.4.6 Bitter taste

$$H_{\text{cal}} = 15.66$$

When degree of freedom (DF) = 5,

$$\chi^2 = 11.070 \text{ (from chi-square table)}$$

Therefore;

$H_{\text{cal}} > H_{\text{table}}$, there is enough evidence to reject H_0 ; can conclude that there is significance difference among the bitter taste of the samples.

4.4.7 Astringent taste

$$H_{\text{cal}} = 4.09$$

When degree of freedom (DF) = 5,

$$\chi^2 = 11.070 \text{ (from chi-square table)}$$

Therefore;

$H_{\text{cal}} < H_{\text{table}}$, there is no enough evidence to reject H_0 ; can conclude that there is no significant difference among the astringent taste of the samples.

It is clearly evident from the sensory results that the variation in taste attributes such as bitter taste and sweet taste exists among different brands. The sweet taste of the arishta indicates the presence of high amount of sugar. No significant differences are found among different brands with respect to odour of the sample. Due to the presence of alcohol in each sample, they have aromatic alcoholic odour.

The refractive index, Brix values, total dissolved solids, reducing sugar and sucrose content and specific gravity values provide information about the concentration of solutes in the samples. Sample C stands out with the highest values of these parameters. This suggests that sample C has a higher sugar content and overall solute concentration. Other than that, sample C may contain a greater amount of herbal extracts or active compounds, potentially making it more potent compared to the other samples.

The samples which have less alcohol percentage should have more reducing sugar. It is evident from the results that sample C with the least amount of alcohol had the highest reducing sugar content and vice versa. It was evident from the sensory results as well that sample C has got the highest sweet taste.

In a previous study it has been shown that when the strength of alcohol increased, the refractive index also increased. (Chinky et al., 2021). But it is contradictory to the results of this study.

Chapter 05

Conclusion

The present investigation evaluated six different brands of ayurvedic commercial preparations of Nimba arishta. Comparative studies on samples of various brands were done based on their physicochemical parameters, organoleptic properties and antioxidant activity.

The investigation showed that organoleptic and various physicochemical parameters such as pH, brix, specific gravity, refractive index, reducing sugar content, apparent sucrose content, total ash, acid-insoluble ash, water soluble ash, total dissolved solid, antioxidant activity and alcohol content etc. were found to be different in leading brands of Nimba arishta.

The study revealed that it may be due to the variations in the formulation or in the production process. But from a similar field study, it has been found that the standard method described in the ayurvedic pharmacopoeia for the preparation of arishta (fig. 2.1) was generally used throughout the country and no other method had been found to be used. (Menike,1995).

It can be concluded that the observed variations in the standardization parameters for evaluating commercially available polyherbal formulations may be attributed to several factors, such as the different ingredients used, sources of herbs or plants used, and their quantities.

This study was done with the aim to understand the variations of these ayurvedic formulations to standardize them. The data evolved in the present study will be very useful for routine quality control of Nimba Arishta. By implementing and embracing standardization and quality control mechanisms, the effectiveness and acceptance of these medications can be further enhanced. Additionally, ensuring the quality and safety measures of these medicines can contribute to their increased efficacy and popularity.

Recommendations

1. Phytochemical constituents and their concentrations should be evaluated among different brands to get a broader insight regarding the variations of composition using quantitative analysis by HPLC / GLC.
2. Microbial testing which includes aerobic plate count, coliform count, yeasts and moulds count and tests for the presence of microbes such as *Escherichia coli*, *Coliforms*, and *Salmonella* should be done to identify the micro-organisms involved in the fermentation process of Nimba arishta and to know whether any contaminations has occurred.
3. Need to be analysed possible contaminations like pesticide residue, heavy metal contaminants such as Hg, Pb, As, and Cd and their concentrations to assess its safety, purity and batch to batch consistency.
4. To uphold and monitor the standards of the preparation, various reference marker compounds and specific fingerprinting techniques can be utilized.
5. Proper addressing of concerns related to the application of these products for patients with diabetes is essential due to their higher sugar content. It is necessary to address questions regarding the suitability of these products for diabetic patients.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 - Minitab project report

1. Physicochemical properties of Nimba arishta samples

One-way ANOVA: pH versus brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal
Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal
Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels Values
brands	6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
brands	5	0.79645	0.159290	183.80	0.000
Error	12	0.01040	0.000867		
Total	17	0.80685			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0294392	98.71%	98.17%	97.10%

Means

brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	3	3.6400	0.0400	(3.6030, 3.6770)
Sample B	3	3.11000	0.01000	(3.07297, 3.14703)

Sample C	3	3.1000	0.0300	(3.0630, 3.1370)
Sample D	3	3.01000	0.01000	(2.97297, 3.04703)
Sample E	3	3.1400	0.0400	(3.1030, 3.1770)
Sample F	3	3.0700	0.0300	(3.0330, 3.1070)

Pooled StDev = 0.0294392

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence brands

N	Mean	Grouping
Sample A	3 3.6400	A
Sample E	3 3.1400	B
Sample B	3 3.11000	B
Sample C	3 3.1000	B
Sample F	3 3.0700	B C
Sample D	3 3.01000	C

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
Sample B - Sample A	-0.5300	0.0240	(-0.6107, -0.4493)	-22.05	0.000
Sample C - Sample A	-0.5400	0.0240	(-0.6207, -0.4593)	-22.47	0.000
Sample D - Sample A	-0.6300	0.0240	(-0.7107, -0.5493)	-26.21	0.000
Sample E - Sample A	-0.5000	0.0240	(-0.5807, -0.4193)	-20.80	0.000
Sample F - Sample A	-0.5700	0.0240	(-0.6507, -0.4893)	-23.71	0.000
Sample C - Sample B	-0.0100	0.0240	(-0.0907, 0.0707)	-0.42	0.998
Sample D - Sample B	-0.1000	0.0240	(-0.1807, -0.0193)	-4.16	0.013
Sample E - Sample B	0.0300	0.0240	(-0.0507, 0.1107)	1.25	0.806
Sample F - Sample B	-0.0400	0.0240	(-0.1207, 0.0407)	-1.66	0.577
Sample D - Sample C	-0.0900	0.0240	(-0.1707, -0.0093)	-3.74	0.026
Sample E - Sample C	0.0400	0.0240	(-0.0407, 0.1207)	1.66	0.577
Sample F - Sample C	-0.0300	0.0240	(-0.1107, 0.0507)	-1.25	0.806
Sample E - Sample D	0.1300	0.0240	(0.0493, 0.2107)	5.41	0.002
Sample F - Sample D	0.0600	0.0240	(-0.0207, 0.1407)	2.50	0.200
Sample F - Sample E	-0.0700	0.0240	(-0.1507, 0.0107)	-2.91	0.104

Individual confidence level = 99.43%

One-way ANOVA: Brix versus Brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal

Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal

Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor **Levels Values**

Brands 6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Brands	5	476.792	95.3583	756.15	0.000
Error	12	1.513	0.1261		
Total	17	478.305			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.355121	99.68%	99.55%	99.29%

Means

Brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	3	25.0667	0.1528	(24.6199, 25.5134)
Sample B	3	29.233	0.252	(28.787, 29.680)
Sample C	3	41.000	0.500	(40.553, 41.447)
Sample D	3	27.400	0.400	(26.953, 27.847)
Sample E	3	30.1000	0.1000	(29.6533, 30.5467)
Sample F	3	27.500	0.500	(27.053, 27.947)

Pooled StDev = 0.355121

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence

Brands	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample C	3	41.000	A
Sample E	3	30.1000	B
Sample B	3	29.233	B
Sample F	3	27.500	C
Sample D	3	27.400	C
Sample A	3	25.0667	D

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
Sample B - Sample A	4.167	0.290	(3.193, 5.141)	14.37	0.000
Sample C - Sample A	15.933	0.290	(14.959, 16.907)	54.95	0.000
Sample D - Sample A	2.333	0.290	(1.359, 3.307)	8.05	0.000
Sample E - Sample A	5.033	0.290	(4.059, 6.007)	17.36	0.000
Sample F - Sample A	2.433	0.290	(1.459, 3.407)	8.39	0.000
Sample C - Sample B	11.767	0.290	(10.793, 12.741)	40.58	0.000
Sample D - Sample B	-1.833	0.290	(-2.807, -0.859)	-6.32	0.000
Sample E - Sample B	0.867	0.290	(-0.107, 1.841)	2.99	0.092

Sample F - Sample B	-1.733	0.290	(-2.707, -0.759)	-5.98	0.001
Sample D - Sample C	-13.600	0.290	(-14.574, -12.626)	-46.90	0.000
Sample E - Sample C	-10.900	0.290	(-11.874, -9.926)	-37.59	0.000
Sample F - Sample C	-13.500	0.290	(-14.474, -12.526)	-46.56	0.000
Sample E - Sample D	2.700	0.290	(1.726, 3.674)	9.31	0.000
Sample F - Sample D	0.100	0.290	(-0.874, 1.074)	0.34	0.999
Sample F - Sample E	-2.600	0.290	(-3.574, -1.626)	-8.97	0.000

Individual confidence level = 99.43%

One-way ANOVA: refractive index versus brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal
 Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor **Levels Values**

brands 6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
brands	5	0.001632	0.000326	3043.84	0.000
Error	12	0.000001	0.000000		
Total	17	0.001633			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0003274	99.92%	99.89%	99.82%

Means

brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	3	1.37250	0.00050	(1.37209, 1.37291)
Sample B	3	1.37980	0.00020	(1.37939, 1.38021)
Sample C	3	1.40190	0.00010	(1.40149, 1.40231)
Sample D	3	1.37693	0.00031	(1.37652, 1.37735)
Sample E	3	1.38140	0.00040	(1.38099, 1.38181)
Sample F	3	1.37670	0.00030	(1.37629, 1.37711)

Pooled StDev = 0.000327448

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence brands

	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample C	3	1.40190	A
Sample E	3	1.38140	B
Sample B	3	1.37980	C
Sample D	3	1.37693	D
Sample F	3	1.37670	D
Sample A	3	1.37250	E

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
Sample B - Sample A	0.007300	0.000267	(0.006402, 0.008198)	27.30	0.000
Sample C - Sample A	0.029400	0.000267	(0.028502, 0.030298)	109.96	0.000
Sample D - Sample A	0.004433	0.000267	(0.003535, 0.005331)	16.58	0.000
Sample E - Sample A	0.008900	0.000267	(0.008002, 0.009798)	33.29	0.000
Sample F - Sample A	0.004200	0.000267	(0.003302, 0.005098)	15.71	0.000
Sample C - Sample B	0.022100	0.000267	(0.021202, 0.022998)	82.66	0.000
Sample D - Sample B	-0.002867	0.000267	(-0.003765, -0.001969)	-10.72	0.000
Sample E - Sample B	0.001600	0.000267	(0.000702, 0.002498)	5.98	0.001
Sample F - Sample B	-0.003100	0.000267	(-0.003998, -0.002202)	-11.59	0.000
Sample D - Sample C	-0.024967	0.000267	(-0.025865, -0.024069)	-93.38	0.000
Sample E - Sample C	-0.020500	0.000267	(-0.021398, -0.019602)	-76.68	0.000
Sample F - Sample C	-0.025200	0.000267	(-0.026098, -0.024302)	-94.25	0.000
Sample E - Sample D	0.004467	0.000267	(0.003569, 0.005365)	16.71	0.000
Sample F - Sample D	-0.000233	0.000267	(-0.001131, 0.000665)	-0.87	0.946
Sample F - Sample E	-0.004700	0.000267	(-0.005598, -0.003802)	-17.58	0.000

Individual confidence level = 99.43%

One-way ANOVA: specific gravity versus Brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal
Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal Significance
level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels Values
Brands	6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Brands	5	0.015935	0.003187	11010.74	0.000
Error	12	0.000003	0.000000		
Total	17	0.015938			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0005380	99.98%	99.97%	99.95%

Means

Brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	3	1.06840	0.00046	(1.06772, 1.06908)
Sample B	3	1.09653	0.00055	(1.09586, 1.09721)
Sample C	3	1.16320	0.00053	(1.16252, 1.16388)
Sample D	3	1.08943	0.00040	(1.08876, 1.09011)
Sample E	3	1.10480	0.00075	(1.10412, 1.10548)
Sample F	3	1.08640	0.00046	(1.08572, 1.08708)

Pooled StDev = 0.000538000

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence

Brands	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample C	3	1.16320	A

Sample E	3 1.10480	B
Sample B	3 1.09653	C
Sample D	3 1.08943	D
Sample F	3 1.08640	E
Sample A	3 1.06840	F

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T- Adjusted	
				Value	P-Value
Sample B - Sample A	0.028133	0.000439	(0.026658, 0.029609)	64.04	0.000
Sample C - Sample A	0.094800	0.000439	(0.093325, 0.096275)	215.81	0.000
Sample D - Sample A	0.021033	0.000439	(0.019558, 0.022509)	47.88	0.000
Sample E - Sample A	0.036400	0.000439	(0.034925, 0.037875)	82.86	0.000
Sample F - Sample A	0.018000	0.000439	(0.016525, 0.019475)	40.98	0.000
Sample C - Sample B	0.066667	0.000439	(0.065191, 0.068142)	151.77	0.000
Sample D - Sample B	-0.007100	0.000439	(-0.008575, -0.005625)	-16.16	0.000
Sample E - Sample B	0.008267	0.000439	(0.006791, 0.009742)	18.82	0.000
Sample F - Sample B	-0.010133	0.000439	(-0.011609, -0.008658)	-23.07	0.000
Sample D - Sample C	-0.073767	0.000439	(-0.075242, -0.072291)	-167.93	0.000
Sample E - Sample C	-0.058400	0.000439	(-0.059875, -0.056925)	-132.95	0.000
Sample F - Sample C	-0.076800	0.000439	(-0.078275, -0.075325)	-174.83	0.000
Sample E - Sample D	0.015367	0.000439	(0.013891, 0.016842)	34.98	0.000
Sample F - Sample D	-0.003033	0.000439	(-0.004509, -0.001558)	-6.91	0.000
Sample F - Sample E	-0.018400	0.000439	(-0.019875, -0.016925)	-41.89	0.000

Individual confidence level = 99.43%

One-way ANOVA: total dissolved solids (g/ml) versus brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal

Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal Significance

level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels Values
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brands	6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F
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Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
brands	5	0.079284	0.015857	1570.06	0.000
Error	12	0.000121	0.000010		

Total 17 0.079405

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0031780	99.85%	99.78%	99.66%

Means

brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	3	0.199333	0.001266	(0.195336, 0.203331)
Sample B	3	0.25223	0.00503	(0.24824, 0.25623)
Sample C	3	0.41067	0.00229	(0.40667, 0.41466)
Sample D	3	0.25343	0.00304	(0.24944, 0.25743)
Sample E	3	0.280600	0.001323	(0.276602, 0.284598)
Sample F	3	0.23867	0.00418	(0.23467, 0.24266)

Pooled StDev = 0.00317796

Tukey Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence brands

	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample C	3	0.41067	A
Sample E	3	0.280600	B
Sample D	3	0.25343	C
Sample B	3	0.25223	C
Sample F	3	0.23867	D
Sample A	3	0.199333	E

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
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Sample B - Sample A	0.05290	0.00259	(0.04418, 0.06162)	20.39	0.000
Sample C - Sample A	0.21133	0.00259	(0.20262, 0.22005)	81.45	0.000
Sample D - Sample A	0.05410	0.00259	(0.04538, 0.06282)	20.85	0.000
Sample E - Sample A	0.08127	0.00259	(0.07255, 0.08998)	31.32	0.000
Sample F - Sample A	0.03933	0.00259	(0.03062, 0.04805)	15.16	0.000
Sample C - Sample B	0.15843	0.00259	(0.14972, 0.16715)	61.06	0.000
Sample D - Sample B	0.00120	0.00259	(-0.00752, 0.00992)	0.46	0.997
Sample E - Sample B	0.02837	0.00259	(0.01965, 0.03708)	10.93	0.000
Sample F - Sample B	-0.01357	0.00259	(-0.02228, -0.00485)	-5.23	0.002
Sample D - Sample C	-0.15723	0.00259	(-0.16595, -0.14852)	-60.60	0.000
Sample E - Sample C	-0.13007	0.00259	(-0.13878, -0.12135)	-50.13	0.000
Sample F - Sample C	-0.17200	0.00259	(-0.18072, -0.16328)	-66.29	0.000
Sample E - Sample D	0.02717	0.00259	(0.01845, 0.03588)	10.47	0.000
Sample F - Sample D	-0.01477	0.00259	(-0.02348, -0.00605)	-5.69	0.001
Sample F - Sample E	-0.04193	0.00259	(-0.05065, -0.03322)	-16.16	0.000

Individual confidence level = 99.43%

WORKSHEET 10

One-way ANOVA: Total ash (%) versus Brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal

Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal

Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor **Levels Values**

Brands 6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Brands	5	3.40496	0.680992	1953.44	0.000
Error	6	0.00209	0.000349		
Total	11	3.40705			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0186711	99.94%	99.89%	99.75%

Means

Brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	2	0.10700	0.00141	(0.07469, 0.13931)
Sample B	2	0.3378	0.0455	(0.3055, 0.3702)
Sample C	2	0.270900	0.000566	(0.238595, 0.303205)
Sample D	2	0.09705	0.00445	(0.06474, 0.12936)
Sample E	2	1.55480	0.00113	(1.52249, 1.58711)
Sample F	2	0.960700	0.000990	(0.928395, 0.993005)

Pooled StDev = 0.0186711

Tukey Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence

Brands	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample E	2	1.55480	A
Sample F	2	0.960700	B
Sample B	2	0.3378	C
Sample C	2	0.270900	C
Sample A	2	0.10700	D
Sample D	2	0.09705	D

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
Sample B - Sample A	0.2308	0.0187	(0.1565, 0.3052)	12.36	0.000
Sample C - Sample A	0.1639	0.0187	(0.0896, 0.2382)	8.78	0.001
Sample D - Sample A	-0.0100	0.0187	(-0.0843, 0.0644)	-0.53	0.992
Sample E - Sample A	1.4478	0.0187	(1.3735, 1.5221)	77.54	0.000
Sample F - Sample A	0.8537	0.0187	(0.7794, 0.9280)	45.72	0.000
Sample C - Sample B	-0.0669	0.0187	(-0.1413, 0.0074)	-3.59	0.076
Sample D - Sample B	-0.2408	0.0187	(-0.3151, -0.1665)	-12.90	0.000
Sample E - Sample B	1.2170	0.0187	(1.1426, 1.2913)	65.18	0.000
Sample F - Sample B	0.6229	0.0187	(0.5485, 0.6972)	33.36	0.000
Sample D - Sample C	-0.1739	0.0187	(-0.2482, -0.0995)	-9.31	0.001
Sample E - Sample C	1.2839	0.0187	(1.2096, 1.3582)	68.76	0.000
Sample F - Sample C	0.6898	0.0187	(0.6155, 0.7641)	36.94	0.000
Sample E - Sample D	1.4578	0.0187	(1.3834, 1.5321)	78.08	0.000
Sample F - Sample D	0.8637	0.0187	(0.7893, 0.9380)	46.26	0.000
Sample F - Sample E	-0.5941	0.0187	(-0.6684, -0.5198)	-31.82	0.000

Individual confidence level = 99.27%

One-way ANOVA: Acid insoluble ash (%) versus Brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal

Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal Significance

level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels	Values
Brands	6	Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
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Brands	5	0.003316	0.000663	2.09	0.199
Error	6	0.001908	0.000318		
Total	11	0.005224			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0178327	63.47%	33.03%	0.00%

Means

Brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	2	0.039900	0.001273	(0.009045, 0.070755)
Sample B	2	0.01350	0.00495	(-0.01735, 0.04435)
Sample C	2	0.04805	0.00997	(0.01720, 0.07890)
Sample D	2	0.01310	0.00410	(-0.01775, 0.04395)
Sample E	2	0.0406	0.0288	(0.0098, 0.0715)
Sample F	2	0.0571	0.0306	(0.0263, 0.0880)

Pooled StDev = 0.0178327

Tukey Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence

Brands	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample F	2	0.0571	A
Sample C	2	0.04805	A
Sample E	2	0.0406	A
Sample A	2	0.039900	A
Sample B	2	0.01350	A
Sample D	2	0.01310	A

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
Sample B - Sample A	-0.0264	0.0178	(-0.0974, 0.0446)	-1.48	0.687
Sample C - Sample A	0.0081	0.0178	(-0.0628, 0.0791)	0.46	0.996

Sample D - Sample A	-0.0268	0.0178	(-0.0978, 0.0442)	-1.50	0.676
Sample E - Sample A	0.0008	0.0178	(-0.0702, 0.0717)	0.04	1.000
Sample F - Sample A	0.0172	0.0178	(-0.0537, 0.0882)	0.97	0.913
Sample C - Sample B	0.0345	0.0178	(-0.0364, 0.1055)	1.94	0.462
Sample D - Sample B	-0.0004	0.0178	(-0.0714, 0.0706)	-0.02	1.000
Sample E - Sample B	0.0271	0.0178	(-0.0438, 0.0981)	1.52	0.666
Sample F - Sample B	0.0436	0.0178	(-0.0273, 0.1146)	2.45	0.271
Sample D - Sample C	-0.0350	0.0178	(-0.1059, 0.0360)	-1.96	0.452
Sample E - Sample C	-0.0074	0.0178	(-0.0784, 0.0636)	-0.41	0.998
Sample F - Sample C	0.0091	0.0178	(-0.0619, 0.0801)	0.51	0.994
Sample E - Sample D	0.0275	0.0178	(-0.0434, 0.0985)	1.54	0.654
Sample F - Sample D	0.0440	0.0178	(-0.0269, 0.1150)	2.47	0.265
Sample F - Sample E	0.0165	0.0178	(-0.0545, 0.0875)	0.93	0.926

Individual confidence level = 99.27%

WORKSHEET 11

One-way ANOVA: water soluble ash versus Brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal

Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels Values
Brands	6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Brands	5	0.011376	0.002275	22.70	0.001
Error	6	0.000601	0.000100		
Total	11	0.011978			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0100114	94.98%	90.80%	79.92%

Means

Brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	2	0.05800	0.01131	(0.04068, 0.07532)
Sample B	2	0.00400	0.00283	(-0.01332, 0.02132)
Sample C	2	0.08775	0.01082	(0.07043, 0.10507)
Sample D	2	0.04440	0.00764	(0.02708, 0.06172)
Sample E	2	0.02800	0.01131	(0.01068, 0.04532)
Sample F	2	0.08990	0.01273	(0.07258, 0.10722)

Pooled StDev = 0.0100114

Tukey Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence

Brands	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample F	2	0.08990	A
Sample C	2	0.08775	A
Sample A	2	0.05800	A B
Sample D	2	0.04440	B
Sample E	2	0.02800	B C
Sample B	2	0.00400	C

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
Sample B - Sample A	-0.0540	0.0100	(-0.0939, -0.0141)	-5.39	0.012
Sample C - Sample A	0.0297	0.0100	(-0.0101, 0.0696)	2.97	0.151
Sample D - Sample A	-0.0136	0.0100	(-0.0535, 0.0263)	-1.36	0.749
Sample E - Sample A	-0.0300	0.0100	(-0.0699, 0.0099)	-3.00	0.147
Sample F - Sample A	0.0319	0.0100	(-0.0080, 0.0718)	3.19	0.119
Sample C - Sample B	0.0837	0.0100	(0.0439, 0.1236)	8.37	0.001
Sample D - Sample B	0.0404	0.0100	(0.0005, 0.0803)	4.04	0.047
Sample E - Sample B	0.0240	0.0100	(-0.0159, 0.0639)	2.40	0.287
Sample F - Sample B	0.0859	0.0100	(0.0460, 0.1258)	8.58	0.001
Sample D - Sample C	-0.0433	0.0100	(-0.0832, -0.0035)	-4.33	0.035
Sample E - Sample C	-0.0597	0.0100	(-0.0996, -0.0199)	-5.97	0.008
Sample F - Sample C	0.0022	0.0100	(-0.0377, 0.0420)	0.21	1.000
Sample E - Sample D	-0.0164	0.0100	(-0.0563, 0.0235)	-1.64	0.607
Sample F - Sample D	0.0455	0.0100	(0.0056, 0.0854)	4.54	0.028
Sample F - Sample E	0.0619	0.0100	(0.0220, 0.1018)	6.18	0.006

Individual confidence level = 99.27%

WORKSHEET 8

One-way ANOVA: Reducing sugar content g invert versus Brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal

Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal Significance

level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels Values
Brands	6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Brands	5	564.733	112.947	1941.66	0.000
Error	12	0.698	0.058		

Total 17 565.431

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.241185	99.88%	99.83%	99.72%

Means

Brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	3	15.749	0.275	(15.445, 16.052)
Sample B	3	24.5447	0.0605	(24.2413, 24.8481)
Sample C	3	34.241	0.486	(33.937, 34.544)
Sample D	3	21.5670	0.1636	(21.2636, 21.8704)
Sample E	3	24.9315	0.0623	(24.6281, 25.2349)
Sample F	3	21.0277	0.0512	(20.7243, 21.3311)

Pooled StDev = 0.241185

Tukey Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence

Brands	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample C	3	34.241	A
Sample E	3	24.9315	B
Sample B	3	24.5447	B
Sample D	3	21.5670	C
Sample F	3	21.0277	C
Sample A	3	15.749	D

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
Sample B - Sample A	8.796	0.197	(8.135, 9.457)	44.67	0.000
Sample C - Sample A	18.492	0.197	(17.830, 19.153)	93.90	0.000
Sample D - Sample A	5.818	0.197	(5.157, 6.480)	29.55	0.000
Sample E - Sample A	9.183	0.197	(8.521, 9.844)	46.63	0.000
Sample F - Sample A	5.279	0.197	(4.618, 5.940)	26.81	0.000

Sample C - Sample B	9.696	0.197	(9.034, 10.357)	49.24	0.000
Sample D - Sample B	-2.978	0.197	(-3.639, -2.316)	-15.12	0.000
Sample E - Sample B	0.387	0.197	(-0.275, 1.048)	1.96	0.413
Sample F - Sample B	-3.517	0.197	(-4.178, -2.856)	-17.86	0.000
Sample D - Sample C	-12.674	0.197	(-13.335, -12.012)	-64.36	0.000
Sample E - Sample C	-9.309	0.197	(-9.970, -8.648)	-47.27	0.000
Sample F - Sample C	-13.213	0.197	(-13.874, -12.551)	-67.10	0.000
Sample E - Sample D	3.365	0.197	(2.703, 4.026)	17.09	0.000
Sample F - Sample D	-0.539	0.197	(-1.201, 0.122)	-2.74	0.138
Sample F - Sample E	-3.904	0.197	(-4.565, -3.242)	-19.82	0.000

Individual confidence level = 99.43%

WORKSHEET 9

One-way ANOVA: Apparent sucrose content versus Brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal

Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal Significance

level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels Values
Brands	6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Brands	5	104.013	20.8026	262.37	0.000
Error	12	0.951	0.0793		
Total	17	104.964			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.281578	99.09%	98.72%	97.96%

Means

Brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	3	1.0728	0.1098	(0.7186, 1.4270)
Sample B	3	0.686	0.212	(0.331, 1.040)
Sample C	3	1.4305	0.0290	(1.0763, 1.7847)
Sample D	3	2.615	0.397	(2.261, 2.969)
Sample E	3	7.698	0.470	(7.343, 8.052)
Sample F	3	3.983	0.197	(3.628, 4.337)

Pooled StDev = 0.281578

Tukey Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence

Brands	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample E	3	7.698	A
Sample F	3	3.983	B
Sample D	3	2.615	C
Sample C	3	1.4305	D
Sample A	3	1.0728	D
Sample B	3	0.686	D

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference	SE of	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
	of Means	Difference			
Sample B - Sample A	-0.387	0.230	(-1.159, 0.385)	-1.68	0.565
Sample C - Sample A	0.358	0.230	(-0.415, 1.130)	1.56	0.639
Sample D - Sample A	1.542	0.230	(0.770, 2.315)	6.71	0.000
Sample E - Sample A	6.625	0.230	(5.853, 7.397)	28.82	0.000
Sample F - Sample A	2.910	0.230	(2.138, 3.682)	12.66	0.000
Sample C - Sample B	0.745	0.230	(-0.027, 1.517)	3.24	0.061
Sample D - Sample B	1.930	0.230	(1.157, 2.702)	8.39	0.000
Sample E - Sample B	7.012	0.230	(6.240, 7.784)	30.50	0.000
Sample F - Sample B	3.297	0.230	(2.525, 4.069)	14.34	0.000
Sample D - Sample C	1.185	0.230	(0.413, 1.957)	5.15	0.003
Sample E - Sample C	6.267	0.230	(5.495, 7.039)	27.26	0.000
Sample F - Sample C	2.552	0.230	(1.780, 3.324)	11.10	0.000
Sample E - Sample D	5.082	0.230	(4.310, 5.855)	22.11	0.000
Sample F - Sample D	1.367	0.230	(0.595, 2.140)	5.95	0.001
Sample F - Sample E	-3.715	0.230	(-4.487, -2.943)	-16.16	0.000

Individual confidence level = 99.43%

One-way ANOVA: Ethanol content (V/V) versus Brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal
Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal
Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels	Values
Brands	6	Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, sample D, sample E, sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Brands	5	9.56667	1.91333	229.60	0.000
Error	6	0.05000	0.00833		
Total	11	9.61667			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0912871	99.48%	99.05%	97.92%

Means

Brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
--------	---	------	-------	--------

Sample A	2	10.400	0.141	(10.242, 10.558)
Sample B	2	9.400	0.000	(9.242, 9.558)
Sample C	2	7.6500	0.0707	(7.4921, 7.8079)
sample D	2	8.800	0.141	(8.642, 8.958)
sample E	2	8.600	0.000	(8.442, 8.758)
sample F	2	9.8500	0.0707	(9.6921, 10.0079)

Pooled StDev = 0.0912871

Tukey Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence

Brands	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample A	2	10.400	A
sample F	2	9.8500	B
Sample B	2	9.400	C
sample D	2	8.800	D
sample E	2	8.600	D
Sample C	2	7.6500	E

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
Sample B - Sample A	-1.0000	0.0913	(-1.3634, -0.6366)	-10.95	0.000
Sample C - Sample A	-2.7500	0.0913	(-3.1134, -2.3866)	-30.12	0.000
sample D - Sample A	-1.6000	0.0913	(-1.9634, -1.2366)	-17.53	0.000
sample E - Sample A	-1.8000	0.0913	(-2.1634, -1.4366)	-19.72	0.000
sample F - Sample A	-0.5500	0.0913	(-0.9134, -0.1866)	-6.02	0.007
Sample C - Sample B	-1.7500	0.0913	(-2.1134, -1.3866)	-19.17	0.000
sample D - Sample B	-0.6000	0.0913	(-0.9634, -0.2366)	-6.57	0.005
sample E - Sample B	-0.8000	0.0913	(-1.1634, -0.4366)	-8.76	0.001
sample F - Sample B	0.4500	0.0913	(0.0866, 0.8134)	4.93	0.019
sample D - Sample C	1.1500	0.0913	(0.7866, 1.5134)	12.60	0.000
sample E - Sample C	0.9500	0.0913	(0.5866, 1.3134)	10.41	0.000
sample F - Sample C	2.2000	0.0913	(1.8366, 2.5634)	24.10	0.000

sample E - sample D	-0.2000	0.0913	(-0.5634, 0.1634)	-2.19	0.357
sample F - sample D	1.0500	0.0913	(0.6866, 1.4134)	11.50	0.000
sample F - sample E	1.2500	0.0913	(0.8866, 1.6134)	13.69	0.000

Individual confidence level = 99.27%

WORKSHEET 13

One-way ANOVA: TPC versus brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal

Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal Significance

level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor **Levels Values**

brands 6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
brands	5	92.1296	18.4259	623.07	0.000
Error	6	0.1774	0.0296		
Total	11	92.3070			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.171967	99.81%	99.65%	99.23%

Means

brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	2	1.7275	0.0262	(1.4300, 2.0250)
Sample B	2	9.036	0.332	(8.738, 9.334)
Sample C	2	8.255	0.186	(7.957, 8.552)
Sample D	2	5.8545	0.0233	(5.5570, 6.1520)
Sample E	2	9.0630	0.0735	(8.7655, 9.3605)
Sample F	2	9.727	0.161	(9.430, 10.025)

Pooled StDev = 0.171967

Tukey Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence brands

	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample F	2	9.727	A
Sample E	2	9.0630	A B
Sample B	2	9.036	B
Sample C	2	8.255	C
Sample D	2	5.8545	D
Sample A	2	1.7275	E

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
Sample B - Sample A	7.309	0.172	(6.624, 7.993)	42.50	0.000
Sample C - Sample A	6.527	0.172	(5.842, 7.212)	37.95	0.000
Sample D - Sample A	4.127	0.172	(3.442, 4.812)	24.00	0.000
Sample E - Sample A	7.335	0.172	(6.651, 8.020)	42.66	0.000
Sample F - Sample A	8.000	0.172	(7.315, 8.685)	46.52	0.000
Sample C - Sample B	-0.782	0.172	(-1.466, -0.097)	-4.54	0.028
Sample D - Sample B	-3.182	0.172	(-3.866, -2.497)	-18.50	0.000
Sample E - Sample B	0.027	0.172	(-0.658, 0.712)	0.16	1.000
Sample F - Sample B	0.691	0.172	(0.007, 1.376)	4.02	0.048
Sample D - Sample C	-2.400	0.172	(-3.085, -1.715)	-13.96	0.000
Sample E - Sample C	0.808	0.172	(0.124, 1.493)	4.70	0.024
Sample F - Sample C	1.473	0.172	(0.788, 2.158)	8.57	0.001
Sample E - Sample D	3.208	0.172	(2.524, 3.893)	18.66	0.000
Sample F - Sample D	3.873	0.172	(3.188, 4.558)	22.52	0.000
Sample F - Sample E	0.665	0.172	(-0.020, 1.349)	3.86	0.057

Individual confidence level = 99.27%

One-way ANOVA: flavonoid content versus Brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal
 Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal Significance
 level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels Values
Brands	6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Brands	5	5.74437	1.14887	541.70	0.000
Error	6	0.01273	0.00212		
Total	11	5.75709			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0460527	99.78%	99.59%	99.12%

Means

Brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	2	1.24105	0.01308	(1.16137, 1.32073)
Sample B	2	3.2151	0.0417	(3.1354, 3.2948)
Sample C	2	2.0306	0.0847	(1.9509, 2.1103)
Sample D	2	1.6043	0.0499	(1.5247, 1.6840)
Sample E	2	2.10040	0.00057	(2.02072, 2.18008)

Sample F 2 2.9279 0.0339 (2.8482, 3.0076)

Pooled StDev = 0.0460527

Tukey Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence

Brands	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample B	2	3.2151	A
Sample F	2	2.9279	B
Sample E	2	2.10040	C
Sample C	2	2.0306	C
Sample D	2	1.6043	D
Sample A	2	1.24105	E

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
Sample B - Sample A	1.9741	0.0461	(1.7907, 2.1574)	42.87	0.000
Sample C - Sample A	0.7895	0.0461	(0.6062, 0.9729)	17.14	0.000
Sample D - Sample A	0.3633	0.0461	(0.1800, 0.5466)	7.89	0.002
Sample E - Sample A	0.8594	0.0461	(0.6760, 1.0427)	18.66	0.000
Sample F - Sample A	1.6869	0.0461	(1.5035, 1.8702)	36.63	0.000
Sample C - Sample B	-1.1845	0.0461	(-1.3678, -1.0012)	-25.72	0.000
Sample D - Sample B	-1.6108	0.0461	(-1.7941, -1.4274)	-34.98	0.000
Sample E - Sample B	-1.1147	0.0461	(-1.2980, -0.9314)	-24.20	0.000
Sample F - Sample B	-0.2872	0.0461	(-0.4705, -0.1039)	-6.24	0.006
Sample D - Sample C	-0.4262	0.0461	(-0.6096, -0.2429)	-9.26	0.001
Sample E - Sample C	0.0698	0.0461	(-0.1135, 0.2531)	1.52	0.669
Sample F - Sample C	0.8973	0.0461	(0.7140, 1.0806)	19.48	0.000
Sample E - Sample D	0.4961	0.0461	(0.3127, 0.6794)	10.77	0.000
Sample F - Sample D	1.3236	0.0461	(1.1402, 1.5069)	28.74	0.000
Sample F - Sample E	0.8275	0.0461	(0.6442, 1.0108)	17.97	0.000

Individual confidence level = 99.27%

One-way ANOVA: proanthocyanidin content (AU) versus Brands

Method

Null hypothesis All means are equal
 Alternative hypothesis Not all means are equal
 Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

Equal variances were assumed for the analysis.

Factor Information

Factor	Levels Values
Brands	6 Sample A, Sample B, Sample C, Sample D, Sample E, Sample F

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Brands	5	0.023130	0.004626	315.86	0.000
Error	6	0.000088	0.000015		

Total 11 0.023218

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0038270	99.62%	99.31%	98.49%

Means

Brands	N	Mean	StDev	95% CI
Sample A	2	0.134900	0.001273	(0.128278, 0.141522)
Sample B	2	0.08970	0.00523	(0.08308, 0.09632)
Sample C	2	0.03748	0.00153	(0.03086, 0.04410)
Sample D	2	0.11488	0.00270	(0.10826, 0.12150)
Sample E	2	0.05054	0.00191	(0.04392, 0.05716)
Sample F	2	0.01027	0.00675	(0.00365, 0.01690)

Pooled StDev = 0.00382699

Tukey Pairwise Comparisons

Grouping Information Using the Tukey Method and 95% Confidence

Brands	N	Mean	Grouping
Sample A	2	0.134900	A
Sample D	2	0.11488	B
Sample B	2	0.08970	C
Sample E	2	0.05054	D
Sample C	2	0.03748	D
Sample F	2	0.01027	E

Means that do not share a letter are significantly different.

Tukey Simultaneous Tests for Differences of Means

Difference of Levels	Difference of Means	SE of Difference	95% CI	Adjusted T-Value	Adjusted P-Value
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Sample B - Sample A	-0.04520	0.00383	(-0.06044, -0.02996)	-11.81	0.000
Sample C - Sample A	-0.09742	0.00383	(-0.11266, -0.08218)	-25.46	0.000
Sample D - Sample A	-0.02002	0.00383	(-0.03526, -0.00478)	-5.23	0.014
Sample E - Sample A	-0.08436	0.00383	(-0.09960, -0.06912)	-22.04	0.000
Sample F - Sample A	-0.12463	0.00383	(-0.13986, -0.10939)	-32.56	0.000
Sample C - Sample B	-0.05222	0.00383	(-0.06746, -0.03698)	-13.65	0.000
Sample D - Sample B	0.02518	0.00383	(0.00994, 0.04042)	6.58	0.005
Sample E - Sample B	-0.03916	0.00383	(-0.05440, -0.02392)	-10.23	0.000
Sample F - Sample B	-0.07942	0.00383	(-0.09466, -0.06419)	-20.75	0.000
Sample D - Sample C	0.07740	0.00383	(0.06216, 0.09264)	20.22	0.000
Sample E - Sample C	0.01306	0.00383	(-0.00218, 0.02830)	3.41	0.092
Sample F - Sample C	-0.02721	0.00383	(-0.04244, -0.01197)	-7.11	0.003
Sample E - Sample D	-0.06434	0.00383	(-0.07958, -0.04910)	-16.81	0.000
Sample F - Sample D	-0.10461	0.00383	(-0.11984, -0.08937)	-27.33	0.000
Sample F - Sample E	-0.04027	0.00383	(-0.05550, -0.02503)	-10.52	0.000

Individual confidence level = 99.27%

Appendix 2 – Ascorbic acid standard curve for DPPH assay of Nimba arishtas

Absorbance of ascorbic acid at different concentrations

Concentration (ppm)	Absorbance (AU)
5	0.090445
15	0.171725
25	0.24016
35	0.31363
45	0.37685

Appendix 3 – DPPH scavenging activity of different market samples of Nimba arishta

Appendix 3 – Tannic acid standard curve

Absorbance of tannic acid at different concentrations

Concentration (ppm)	Absorbance (AU)
1	0.090445
2	0.171725
3	0.24016
4	0.31363
5	0.37685

Appendix 4 – Flavonoid standard curve

Absorbance of quercetin at different concentrations

Quercetin Standard ($\mu\text{g} / \text{mL}$)	Absorbance (AU)
12.20	0.215715
18.30	0.347085
24.40	0.471265
30.50	0.609385
36.60	0.72672

Appendix 5 – Ethanol content (V/V%) of the samples using GC - FID

Sample: NIMBARISHTAYA_A

Trial	Peak Area of Sample (A _s)	Peak Area of Internal STD (A _{IS})	A _s /A _{IS}	Ethanol % (V/V)
R1	1374.41	1287.68	1.0674	10.3
R2	1351.94	1244.98	1.0859	10.5

Sample: NIMBARISHTAYA B

Trial	Peak Area of Sample (A _s)	Peak Area of Internal STD (A _{IS})	A _s /A _{IS}	Ethanol % (V/V)
R1	1229.08	1268.49	0.9689	9.4
R2	1385.25	1420.13	0.9754	9.4

Sample: NIMBARISHTAYA_C

Trial	Peak Area of Sample (A _s)	Peak Area of Internal STD (A _{IS})	A _s /A _{IS}	Ethanol % (V/V)
R1	984.63	1246.65	0.7898	7.7
R2	918.53	1179.12	0.779	7.6

Sample: NIMBARISHTAYA_D

Trial	Peak Area of Sample (A _s)	Peak Area of Internal STD (A _{IS})	A _s /A _{IS}	Ethanol % (V/V)
R1	1111.04	1238.68	0.897	8.7
R2	1156.03	1263.09	0.9152	8.9

Sample: NIMBARISHTAYA_E

Trial	Peak Area of Sample (A _s)	Peak Area of Internal STD (A _{IS})	A _s /A _{IS}	Ethanol % (V/V
R1	1076.58	1214.15	0.8867	8.6
R2	1149.68	1300.36	0.8841	8.6

Sample: NIMBARISHTAYA_F

Trial	Peak Area of Sample (A _s)	Peak Area of Internal STD (A _{IS})	A _s /A _{IS}	Ethanol %(V/V
R1	1253.95	1239.88	1.0113	9.8
R2	1351.71	1314.27	1.0285	9.9

Appendix 6 : Radar charts showing the results of sensory analysis among six commercial samples of Nimba arishta

Intensity scale –

1 – very weak

2 – weak

3 – medium strong

4 – strong

5 – very strong

Appendix 7 - Sensory evaluation form

Name _____ :

Test subject no : _____

Date _____ :

Time : _____

Sample code	Sensory Parameter	Test quality	Intensity
A	Odour	Herbaceous odour	
		Medicinal odour	
		Aromatic odour	
	Taste	Sour taste	
		Sweet taste	
		Bitter taste	
		Astringent taste	
B	Odour	Herbaceous odour	
		Medicinal odour	
		Aromatic odour	
	Taste	Sour taste	
		Sweet taste	
		Bitter taste	
		Astringent taste	
C	Odour	Herbaceous odour	
		Medicinal odour	
		Aromatic odour	
	Taste	Sour taste	
		Sweet taste	
		Bitter taste	
		Astringent taste	

Intensity scale –

1 – very weak

2 – weak

3 – medium strong

4 – strong

5 – very strong

You will receive six samples. Please rank them in order of intensity for the given parameter. Start by determining the approximate intensity of each sample and applying the given intensity scale. Note that two samples may have the same intensity.

D	Odour	Herbaceous odour	
		Medicinal odour	
		Aromatic odour	
	Taste	Sour taste	
		Sweet taste	
		Bitter taste	
		Astringent taste	
E	Odour	Herbaceous odour	
		Medicinal odour	
		Aromatic odour	
	Taste	Sour taste	
		Sweet taste	
		Bitter taste	
		Astringent taste	
F	Odour	Herbaceous odour	
		Medicinal odour	
		Aromatic odour	
	Taste	Sour taste	
		Sweet taste	
		Bitter taste	
		Astringent taste	

